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M.Sc. Thesis

Properties of Kelvin Waves forecast errors in the ECMWF deterministic forecasts.

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Topic

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Abstract

Kelvin waves (KWs) are eastward-propagating planetary-scale features associated with significant variability of the tropical atmosphere. They are known to be essential ingredients of tropical circulation such as the El-Niño southern oscillation (ENSO), the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) and the Madden-Julian oscillation (MJO) and are continuously forced by convection in the troposphere. Convection also constitutes a challenge for numerical weather prediction, ultimately affecting forecast skill in the tropics. The impact of poor convection simulation on tropical predictability is nonetheless still matter of ongoing research. This work investigates KWs forecast errors and is branched in two research questions. One asks to what extent KWs forecast errors reflect errors in simulated convection. A second one asks whether the spectral coefficients allow to investigate forecast errors attributable to phase shifts. We use ECMWF deterministic forecasts covering the period from November, 2021 to September, 2022; 00 UTC analyses are used to validate 10-day long forecasts. KWs spectral coefficients are obtained from the operational MODES analysis of ECMWF deterministic forecasts. OLR is used as a proxy for deep tropical convection and is verified against NOAA daily observations over the 2019-2021 period. Results show a close reflection of systematic errors in OLR and KW fields in several tropical regions. For the KW, these concern progressively deeper layers of the upper tropopause and lower stratosphere as forecast lead time increases. In the lower stratosphere, KW in forecasts is systematically shifted westward than in analysis, indicating a tendency toward too slow predicted propagation.

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1. Introduction

Kelvin waves (KWs) are the slowest eigensolutions of the linearized rotating shallow water (LRSW) problem on a rotating sphere (Matsuno 1966), also called Hough harmonics. KWs alone are known to incorporate up to 30% of the planetary-scale non-Rossby tropical atmospheric variability (Stephan et al. 2021). Spanning across a wide range of temporal scales, they are planetary-scale propagators of diabatic forcing occurring in the troposphere (Gill 1980; Holton and Lindzen 1972).

KWs are a significant components of the El-Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and a relevant explanatory factor for the Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO). In addition to that, KWs are also the main dynamical component describing Madden-Julian Oscillations (MJO). Their prediction is therefore with no doubt of interest for tropical weather predictability and its impact on higher latitudes.

In the LRSW system, KWs are eastward-propagating features with a linear dispersion relation. They are confined within tropical latitudes due to the sharp meridional increase of the Coriolis term, in what Matsuno (1966) called an ‘equatorial duct’. Along the equator, they have been observed in deep tropical convection, using outgoing long-wave radiation (OLR) as a proxy (see *e.g.* Wheeler and Kiladis (1999)) as well as in precipitation (*e.g.* Dias et al. (2018)) and dynamical fields (*e.g.* Flannaghan and Fueglistaler (2013)).

In the troposphere and lower tropopause layer (TTL), KWs are coupled with deep moist convection as a slowly propagating disturbance (Andrews et al. 1987; Kiladis et al. 2009; Wheeler and Kiladis 1999). Propagation of KWs in the stratosphere is instead closer to a regime of freely propagating internal gravity waves, whose forcing is located in the lower TTL. This last regime constitutes also the largest share of KW variability (Flannaghan and Fueglistaler 2013; Stephan et al. 2021; Žagar et al. 2016; Žagar et al. 2022).

Since the 1960s, researchers developed several filtering techniques to extract spectral coefficients for equatorial waves (Knippertz et al. 2022). Some, such as frequency-wavenumber filtering (FWF), use Fourier transformation in time and space to match 2D waves on the dispersion diagram. Differently, 3D normal modes (3DNM) decomposition provides a set of static 2D pictures for each vertical vibrational mode, and wave characterization is provided by projection onto Hough harmonics.

Forecasting of large-scale features have certainly benefited from advances in numerical weather prediction (NWP), also thanks to massively improved grid resolutions. This, together with the introduction of ensemble forecasting, has been recognized to push fore-

cast skills in certain scenarios also beyond theoretical limits explored in the 1960-80s (Buizza and Leutbecher 2015; Holton 2004; Lorenz 1982).

Atmospheric predictability is nonetheless far from homogeneous across time and space scales, seasonality and latitudes. The tropics, despite being characterized by large predictability in long-range (> 10 days) forecasts have typically faster error growth in the short range (< 5 days) (Buizza and Leutbecher 2015; Judt 2020; Kalnay 2003; Shukla 1981), primarily due to large uncertainties in the initial states (Žagar et al. 2015a; Žagar 2017).

Geostrophic balance, which constitutes a weak relationship in the tropics, together with imperfect convection schemes directly affecting correlations during the assimilation phase, have been associated to the larger analysis errors in the tropics than in the middle-latitudes (Kalnay 2003; Lorenz 1963; Žagar 2017; Žagar et al. 2005, 2015b). For this reason improved assimilation for the tropical atmosphere is currently a promising area of investigation, especially concerning wind observations, as shown by Žagar et al. (2021).

Research related to predictability and forecast verification has largely recurred to several spectral representations (*e.g.* Buizza and Leutbecher (2015)) to show dependence on spatial scales. Such advantage is featured also by representations such as FWF or 3DNM. These are also based on physically meaningful structures, whose dynamical properties are well-defined at least in the simplified model of the atmosphere provided by the LRSW system. Nonetheless, a study by Dias et al. (2018) on precipitation forecasts is so far the only one to our knowledge investigating forecast errors for separate equatorial waves.

Along this line, this work explores KW forecast errors in dynamical output fields from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather (ECMWF) deterministic forecasts.

A first research question concerns whether KW short-range forecast errors can be associated to errors in simulated convection. In order to do this, OLR is used as a proxy for deep tropical convection, and signal in forecasts is verified against daily observational data. The association is done by selecting OLR ‘footprints’, *i.e.* recognizable planetary- and synoptic-scale convective-related patterns. These footprints are then compared with systematic and root-mean-squared forecast errors (RMSE) for the KW.

A second research question stems from observing that, for spectral coefficients in polar notation, it is possible to interpret the phase as a zonal shift of the wave pattern. For the KWs, phase evolution incorporates linear eastward wavefront propagation. Hence, we explore the possibility to investigate errors in terms of systematic anticipation or delay of wave patterns. This is done by developing a method for separating errors into a phase and an amplitude contribution, and finally applying it to vertical KW profiles.

For this work, we use ECMWF 10 days high resolution (HRES) deterministic forecasts decomposed with MODES (Žagar et al. 2015a), a software that implements 3DNM decomposition as described by Kasahara and Puri 1981. The KW is filtered by selection of the corresponding spectral coefficients in 3DNM representation. The covered period is September, 2019 to September, 2022. For each forecast, 00UTC analysis at the correspond-

ing validity date is used as verifying field. Simulated OLR is computed from the top net thermal radiation (TTR) HRES field and verified against daily OLR observations from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) climate data records (CDR). The spanned period for OLR data is January, 2019 to December, 2021.

2. Theory

2.1. Kelvin waves

The Kelvin Wave (KW) is formally defined as a solution of the linearized rotating shallow water (LRSW) problem. Here follows a brief presentation of it and its solutions in the case of the equatorial beta-plane. Then follows an overview of the theory of tropospheric KW.

2.1.1. Equatorial waves

Large scale motion in the atmosphere is characterized by typical length scale far larger than the vertical motion. If the Earth was to be scaled down to the size of an apple, the atmosphere would be no thicker than its skin. This justifies considering many scales of motion in the atmosphere as nearly flat, and the rotating shallow water model offers the tools to build a simplified representation of such an atmosphere.

In a rotating shallow water (RSW) model, the horizontal velocity and length scales far exceed the corresponding vertical quantities.

$$\frac{d\mathbf{V}}{dt} + f\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{V} = -g\nabla h \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{dh}{dt} + D(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{V}) = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

Where $\frac{d}{dt}$ indicates the material derivative and $\mathbf{V} = (u, v)$ is the horizontal velocity field, where u is the zonal and v the meridional wind. ∇ is defined according to the chosen reference along the zonal and meridional direction. h is the depth field, with mean value D , and $f = 2\Omega$ is the Coriolis parameter with Ω the Earth's angular velocity, in the general case a function of latitude.

The RSW model provides a description of oscillations whose restoring force are to be attributed to two different mechanisms: the first one, is the gravity force, visible on the right-hand side (RHS) of equation 2.1; the second one, is the Coriolis force, appearing in the second term of the same equation 2.1.

The RSW equations can be rewritten in a linearized form in the perturbation variables,

the linearized rotating shallow water (LRSW) equations:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{V} \equiv \mathbf{0} + (u', v') \\ h = D + h' \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{V}'}{\partial t} - f \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{V}' = -g \nabla h' \quad (2.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial h'}{\partial t} + D(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{V}') = 0 \quad (2.5)$$

Where the primed variables express perturbation quantities. These equations constitute the homogeneous part of the LRSW equations, and have no general analytical solution.

The equatorial beta-plane.

It is possible to simplify the LRSW so that it admits analytical solutions. Let's approximate the Coriolis parameter f in equation 2.4 a function of latitude close to the equator:

$$f(y) = f(0) + \frac{df}{dy}(0) y + o\left(\frac{df}{dy}\right) \sim \beta y \quad (2.6)$$

$$\beta \equiv \frac{df}{dy}(0) \quad (2.7)$$

This defines the so-called equatorial beta-plane, and the linearized Coriolis parameter approximates the actual value within an error of 10% in the tropical 30°N-S belt.

Solutions to the LRSW equation 2.4 and 2.5 on the equatorial beta-plane can be expressed in the following form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u' \\ v' \\ h' \end{pmatrix} = \boldsymbol{\psi}(y) e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (2.8)$$

where the meridional dependence is given by Hermite functions $\boldsymbol{\psi}(y)$ (Matsuno 1966). Solutions are characterized by the following dispersion relation:

$$\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} - k\beta - \omega k^2 = (2n + 1) \frac{\beta}{c} \omega \quad \text{with } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (2.9)$$

where the scale speed $c \equiv gD$ has been defined. n identifies the meridional structure function (MSF), which corresponds to the n -th Hermite function. These describe motion confined on the equatorial belt, acting as a wave-guide for propagation (Matsuno 1966). Waves defined by dispersion relation 2.9 can be classified in several regimes. Figure 2.1 shows relation 2.9 on a dispersion diagram, for several solutions of the LRSW problem, as reported in Knippertz et al. (2022).

Equatorial inertio-gravity waves When $n \neq 0$ in the dispersion relation 2.9, the limit of large ω identifies rapidly propagating inertio-gravity (IG) waves:

$$\omega_{IG} \sim \sqrt{c^2 k^2 + (2n + 1)\beta c} \quad (2.10)$$

Where the short-wave regime can be approximated by a non-dispersive, rapidly propagating purely-inertial mode:

$$\omega_{IG} \sim ck \quad \text{with large } k \quad (2.11)$$

Equatorial Rossby waves When $n \neq 0$ in the dispersion relation 2.9, in the limit of large ω one obtains the following approximation of the dispersion relation

$$\omega_{ROS} \sim \frac{-k\beta}{k^2 + (2n + 1)\frac{\beta}{c}} \quad (2.12)$$

which describes slowly, westward propagating, equatorial Rossby waves (RW).

Modes separation A compelling property of the IG and Rossby regimes is that they are separated by a frequency gap. In the two cases, the value $n = 1$ defines respectively the slowest IG and the fastest Rossby waves, whose difference is given, at $k = 0$ by:

$$\omega_{IG}(k = 0, n = 1) - \omega_{ROS}(k = 0, n = 1) = \sqrt{3\beta c} \quad (2.13)$$

This allows to distinguish neatly the two regimes during in practical applications.

Mixed Rossby-gravity wave. When $n = 0$, the dispersion relation is given by:

$$\omega_{MRG;1,2} = \frac{kc}{2} \left(1 \pm \sqrt{1 + \frac{4\beta c}{k^2 c^2}} \right) \quad (2.14)$$

which describes a uniquely equatorial mode, the mixed Rossby-gravity (MRG) wave. Its meridional structure is given by the first anti-symmetrical Hermite function.

Equatorial Kelvin wave. A special solution is found when imposing purely zonal wind field in the LSW model on the beta-plane, *i.e.* when $v' = 0$ in equations 2.4 and 2.5. Such solution s given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u' \\ h' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{gD} \\ D \end{pmatrix} \mathcal{A} e^{-\left(\frac{\beta}{2c}\right)y^2} e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (2.15)$$

and whose dispersion relation is linear and given by:

$$\omega = gDk \quad (2.16)$$

describing a non-dispersive, eastward propagating equatorial wave. On the dispersion diagram, KWs are located on straight lines (see figure 2.1). Its meridional structure is given by the first symmetrical Hermite function.

Such behaviour recalls that of oceanic Kelvin waves, propagating along coastal lines with the velocity of long-wave gravity waves. In such setting, the equatorial Kelvin wave obeys to the same principle, and uses the equatorial beta-plane as a virtual boundary: the ‘equatorial duct’ (Matsuno 1966).

2.1.2. KWs in the tropics

Right after Matsuno’s 1966 work on equatorial waves from the LRSW problem, prominent research groups in the late 1960s aimed at assessing whether equatorial Kelvin and MRG waves could be observed in the tropical atmosphere. Eventually, their existence could be proved thanks to the work of Yanai and Wallace, respectively at the University of Tokyo and at the University of Washington (Kasahara 2020).

In the tropical atmosphere, KWs incorporate most of the observed eastward-propagating disturbances along the ITCZ. Historically, they are attributed an intrinsic phase speed with respect to the zonal flow around 50 m/s, a typical period of 15 days and a meridional scale of 1300 – 1700 km (Andrews et al. 1987). From the reference of the ground, KWs are observed to modulate convection and precipitation at their passage, and to be associated with increasingly organized, large and intensive convective cells as they approach (Straub and Kiladis 2002).

In recent reanalysis fields, it has been observed that KWs, together with MRG waves, incorporate at least 30% of the subseasonal, planetary and synoptic-scale ($k = 1, \dots, 16$) non-Rossby tropical variance (Stephan et al. 2021). The same study shows that the same share of variance at the planetary scales ($k = 1, \dots, 5$) is given by the KW alone.

Fast and Slow motion

As mentioned *supra*, the LRSW problem shows a formal distinction between slow, RW modes and fast, IG waves. This concept plays a major role in NWP, where fast-propagating modes are filtered out from the initialization fields, since the model cannot properly resolve their high frequency (Tribbia 2020).

However, the LRSW problem on the equatorial beta-plane also illustrates that KWs obey to a linear dispersion relation, spanning a wide range of scales for the phase propagation speed. This implies that a description in terms of fast and slow waves is not possible concerning KW modes. A similar observation concerns also the MRG and the first eastward IG modes, spanning all scales of interests on the dispersion diagram.

These modes are therefore completely immune to such separation of dynamical regimes. As a consequence, they constitute a necessary ingredient even for the most simplified models for the tropical atmosphere (Stephan et al. 2021).

Upward energy transport

Large scale KWs are known to originate from diabatic forcing located in the troposphere (Gill 1980). Within this framework, they are described as propagators, in time and space, of perturbations coming from diabatic heating.

Propagation of KWs in the upper levels of the atmosphere coincides with upward energy transport. This mechanism is one of the main explanatory factors (Holton and Lindzen 1972) for the quasi-biennial oscillations (QBOs), inversions in the zonal wind direction in the upper troposphere with a period around 22 months; in particular, Giorgetta et al. (2002) were able to reproduce QBOs from diabatic forcing of a selection of equatorial waves, including the KW, and showed that such upward momentum transfer is to be attributed to the shortest-scale vertical modes.

Internal gravity waves Upward propagation of KWs can be described with the formalism of internal linear gravity waves. For the KW holds a simplified form (Flannaghan and Fueglistaler 2013; Ryu et al. 2008; Stephan et al. 2021) of the Taylor-Goldstein equation in a zonally constant horizontal wind field u_0 ¹:

$$\frac{d^2 w}{dz^2} = - \left[\frac{N^2 k^2}{\Omega^2} \right] w \quad (2.17)$$

where w is the wind perturbation along the vertical direction z , $N^2 = \frac{g}{\theta} \frac{d\theta}{dz}$ is the buoyancy frequency as function of potential temperature θ , k the zonal wavenumber. Ω is here the intrinsic frequency, and is that of the wave in the inertial reference of the background wind:

$$\Omega \equiv \omega - k u_0 \quad (2.18)$$

where ω is the Doppler-shifted frequency, measured in the reference frame of the ground.

Plugging the following wave Ansatz in equation 2.17:

$$w = W e^{imz} \quad W, m \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2.19)$$

yields the following dispersion relations:

$$\Omega = (\omega - k u_0) = \pm N k / m \quad (2.20)$$

where the two solutions come from the extraction of the squared root. In the case of a gravity wave transporting momentum upward, the vertical component of the group velocity is expected to be positive, which means that the phase speed must be directed downward:

$$c_z = \omega / m < 0 \Rightarrow m < 0 \quad (2.21)$$

¹This is obtained from the solution of the atmospheric polarization equations. For derivation and general discussion, see *e.g.* Nappo (2002).

For a KW, k and Ω are positive, which implies that only the negative root of the dispersion relation 2.20 can be retained. Finally, by identifying the zonal phase speed $c \equiv \omega/k$ (typically smaller than 25 m/s), the following relation holds:

$$c - u_0 = \left(-\frac{N}{m}\right) > 0 \Rightarrow c > u_0 \quad (2.22)$$

which tells that upward propagation is not possible if the background wind is larger than c . Also, for a given value of the buoyancy frequency N , longer wavelengths are admitted as long as $c - u_0$ is large enough. This provides an intuitive explanation of the fact that upward propagation of KWs is facilitated by an easterly background². This mechanism has been used to explain amplification of KW variability in regions of easterlies background, and observed for the KW in ECMWF reanalysis fields (Blaauw and Žagar 2018; Flannaghan and Fueglistaler 2013; Žagar et al. 2022).

2.1.3. Coupling with convection

Since the late 1960s studies on the KW, effort has been spent on investigating the interplay between KW propagation and diabatic forcing (Gill 1980; Holton and Lindzen 1972). This research focused on the KWs as the dynamical response to typical tropospheric tropical diabatic heating.

CCEWs

Gill (1980) modelled diabatic heating as a source term in the RHS of the continuity equation 2.5, so that that vertical motion associated to heated air parcels can enter the LSW equations and be translated into a wave response. The observed response induced the author to describe the KW as a carrier of information about the localized diabatic heat, peaking around 5 km altitude.

Eventually, this came to take shape in the form of a very successful concept, that of convectively-coupled equatorial waves (CCEWs). CCEWs is a term introduced by Wheeler and Kiladis (1999), who showed propagation of convective signal along equatorial modes by applying frequency-wavenumber filtering (FWF) to equatorial OLR signal.

CCEWs enshrine the idea that some large scale equatorial modes appear entangled to convective signal in the tropics, especially along the ITCZ. However, despite a general understanding (see *e.g.* Kiladis et al. (2009), Straub and Kiladis (2002)), coupling mechanisms at different scales of CCEWs are still not clarified by theory (Nakamura and

²More precisely, Ryu et al. (2008) derive an expression for the integrated wave energy density E as a function of the phase speed c , background wind u_0 and zonal wavenumber k for the case of slowly varying $u_0(y)$ using WKB approximation:

$$\frac{c}{k} \frac{E}{(c - u_0)} \approx \text{constant along } x \quad (2.23)$$

so that large values of E are obtained for $u_0 < 0$.

Takayabu 2022).

Theoretical and observed KWs clearly show some fundamental differences, since the first come from the simplified picture of the LRSW problem. These will emerge several times *infra*, but two of them can be mentioned at this stage.

Observed KWs propagate only to a first approximation in a symmetrical fashion, if nothing else because the ITCZ is typically off the equator by 5 to 15 degrees (Straub and Kiladis 2002). A second point concerning KWs is that they have a non-negligible meridional wind component around the deep convective zone; this component mainly projecting on Rossby modes (Straub and Kiladis 2002).

Equivalent depths In order to describe the 3D atmosphere with the LRSW problem, a decomposition is performed by projecting the 3D field along vertical structure functions (VSF, refer to appendix A). Each VSF is associated a mode number m and an equivalent depth, D_m , which ultimately constitutes a parameter for the LRSW problem. The m -th equivalent depth is associated to a particular vibration mode along the vertical direction, characterized by m crossing of the zero value; it also associated to particular dynamical properties, obtained by plugging D_m into the dispersion relation 2.9. For the KW, this translates directly into determining the phase speed in the LRSW model: $c \equiv \sqrt{gD_m}$.

Typically observed tropospheric diabatic heating is confined in the troposphere between 250 hPa and 850 hPa, primarily projecting on a barotropic and first baroclinic mode (Kiladis et al. 2009): this implies theoretically a frequency selection (Andrews et al. 1987) on the equivalent depth of generated KWs, defining values of ~ 250 m and ~ 50 m for the two modes. However, dynamical response observed via FWF is shallower, with observed equivalent depths respectively of ~ 50 m and ~ 25 m (Kiladis et al. 2009; Wheeler and Kiladis 1999).

This led Straub and Kiladis (2002) to the hypothesis that, due to the moist convective coupling, temperature fields and stability are perturbed by vertical advection of moisture. Such hypothesis has been supported by observations of a vertical modulation in the convectively-available potential energy (CAPE), eventually responsible for a response shallower than expected by dry theory.

On top of that, there is also a limit on the equivalent depth of KWs set by zonal wind background, as seen *supra*. The role of QBO is to modulate a cut-off in phase speed associated to zonal wind vertical shear (Andrews et al. 1987); consequently, a KW vertical wavelength can be limited between 2 km in the most westerly QBO phase, and 10 km in the extreme easterly QBO phase (Wheeler and Kiladis 1999).

2.2. 3D normal mode representation

The LRSW problem on the sphere can be written in vector notation as (Kasahara 2020):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{t}} \mathbf{W} + L\mathbf{W} = 0 \quad (2.24)$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{v} \\ \tilde{h} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.25)$$

where all fields are meant as perturbation quantities and $L(D_m, \phi, \lambda)$ is a linear differential operator depending on the coordinates and the equivalent depth parameter (see A for a definition). Superscripts \sim indicate the nondimensional dynamical variables of the problem:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{v} \\ \tilde{h} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{gD_m} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sqrt{gD_m} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/D_m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ h \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{D}_m^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ h \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.26)$$

where the operator \mathcal{D}_m , transforming from non-dimensional to dimension fields has been defined for every equivalent depth D_m . Equations 2.24, 2.25 are normally referred to as the horizontal structure equations (HSE).

2.2.1. Solutions of the HSE

The solution for the HSE for a given vertical mode m and equivalent depth D_m is written as:

$$\mathbf{W}(\lambda, \phi, \tilde{t}) = \mathbf{H}_\nu(\lambda, \phi) e^{-i\omega_\nu \tilde{t}} \quad \nu = (k, m, n) \quad (2.27)$$

where Einstein's notation on repeated indices has been used. $\mathbf{H}_\nu(\lambda, \phi)$ are eigenfunctions for the operator L and are called horizontal structure functions or Hough harmonics. ω_ν is the frequency associated to a specific mode and expresses the temporal evolution of \mathbf{H}_ν in the LRSW system.

The horizontal structure equations formally constitute a Sturm-Liouville's problem on the spherical surface (see appendix A), therefore its solutions are a complete set for the space L^2 of functions on it. Therefore, Hough harmonics can be used to expand any function of the dynamical fields in the atmosphere, as long as their squared norm (or their associated perturbation energy, as observed *infra*) is finite. Moreover, Hough harmonics dependency on λ and ϕ can be separated:

$$\mathbf{H}_n^k(\lambda, \phi) = \Theta_n(\phi) e^{ik\lambda} \quad (2.28)$$

where k and n are, respectively, the zonal and meridional index. The vertical mode index m is for this discussion left implicit, since each m defines a separate horizontal problem.

Along the zonal direction, Hough harmonics are Fourier base harmonics on a circular domain; their meridional dependence, instead, is given by the Hough vector functions or meridional structure functions (MSF), that entangle together the dynamical fields:

$$\Theta_n^k(\phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u}_n^k(\phi) \\ i\tilde{v}_n^k(\phi) \\ \tilde{h}_n^k(\phi) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2.29)$$

In the tropics, MSFs are approximated by solutions of the LRSW problem on the beta plane expressed by Hermite functions (Matsuno 1966).

Formally, Hough harmonics are orthonormal with respect to the following inner product:

$$(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) \equiv \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} d\lambda \int_{-1}^1 d\mu (\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}^*) \quad \text{where } \mu = \sin \phi \quad (2.30)$$

where (\cdot) is the ordinary scalar product and $*$ indicates the complex conjugate. The symbol \oint will be used to express the integral on the unit sphere appearing in equation 2.30. In index notation orthonormality is expressed by:

$$(\mathbf{H}_n^k, \mathbf{H}_{n'}^{k'}) = \delta_{k,k'} \delta_{n,n'} \quad (2.31)$$

Finally, any L^2 function $f = (\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{h})(\lambda, \phi)$ can be expressed as a linear combination of Hough harmonics:

$$f(\lambda, \phi) = \hat{f}_n^k \mathbf{H}_n^k(\lambda, \phi) \quad \hat{f}_n^k \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2.32)$$

Where the λ_n^k are called Hough coefficients of the function f , *i.e.* the function f in Hough representation.

Norm and energy

For a given vertical mode m , the global inner product 2.30 induces the following squared norm :

$$\begin{aligned} gD_m(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x})_m &= |\hat{f}_m|^2 = gD_m \hat{f}_{n,m}^k (\hat{f}_{n,m}^k)^* \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \oint d\mu u^2 + v^2 + \frac{g}{D_m} h^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.33)$$

where as usual \oint is the integral on the unit sphere. For what follows, $\hat{f}_v^2 = |\hat{f}_v|^2$.

The defined squared norm has dimension of m^5/s^2 or J/Kg , and is proportional to the total perturbation energy associated to the mode. It is possible to recognize a kinetic (K)

and potential (P) energy contribution (Žagar et al. 2015a) to equation 2.33:

$$I_{tot,m} \equiv \frac{1}{2}gD(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) = \oint K + Pd\Sigma \quad (2.34)$$

$$K \equiv \frac{1}{2}(u^2 + v^2) \quad (2.35)$$

$$P \equiv \frac{1}{2}(gh^2) \quad (2.36)$$

so that the necessary condition for a vector field $\mathbf{f} = (\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{h})(\lambda, \phi)$ to be decomposed into Hough harmonics is that it contains finite perturbation energy.

The perturbation energy 2.34 associated to a single mode $\nu = (k, n, m)$ is expressed in modal space as:

$$I_{tot,\nu} = \frac{1}{2}gD_m(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x})_\nu = \frac{1}{2}gD_m(\hat{f}_\nu)^2 \quad (2.37)$$

And the total perturbation energy for a vertical mode m :

$$I_{tot,\mu} = \sum_{k,n} I_\nu \quad (2.38)$$

Vertical structure As seen *supra*, for every vertical mode m an equivalent depth D_m is defined; the vertical dependency is then by vertical structure functions (VSFs, refer to A for a reference or Kasahara (2020) for a complete description) in sigma coordinates:

$$G \equiv G_m(\sigma) \quad (2.39)$$

$$\sigma = p/p_s \quad \sigma \in [0, 1] \quad (2.40)$$

where p and p_s are, respectively, the pressure coordinate and the surface pressure. The extreme values of σ are 1 at the surface and 0 at the top of the atmosphere. $G_m(\sigma)$ also constitute an orthonormal complete set for L^2 functions on the domain $[0, 1]$.

Therefore, an L^2 function $f(\lambda, \phi, \sigma)$ with domain in R^3 is finally given in 3D normal mode representation (3DNM) as:

$$\mathbf{f}(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) = \hat{f}_{n,m}^k \mathbf{H}_{n,m}^k(\lambda, \phi) G_m(\sigma) \quad \hat{f}_{n,m}^k \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2.41)$$

where $\hat{f}_{n,m}^k$ are referred to, in this work, with the name of spectral coefficients.

The condition for decomposition in 3DNMs is that the associated perturbation energy on the unitary sphere is finite:

$$\sum_m I_{tot,m} = \left(\int_0^1 d\sigma \oint K + Pd\Sigma \right) < \infty \quad (2.42)$$

where the Parseval's identity for the representation into VSFs has been used:

$$f(\sigma) = a_m G_m(\sigma) \quad (2.43)$$

$$\int_0^1 f(\sigma) d\sigma = \sum_m (a_m)^2 \quad (2.44)$$

2.2.2. Wave filtering

The procedure for computing Hough harmonics is described by Kasahara and Puri (1981) and has been implemented in an open-source piece of software by Žagar et al. (2015) called MODES. Thanks to it, we can represent dynamical atmospheric field into 3DNM representation, in the form of Hough coefficients.

Wave types

As seen *supra*, the zonal dependency of Hough coefficients coincides with a real Fourier transform on the periodic domain along longitude. The MSFs, instead, are the most important peculiarity of 3DNM representation.

Hough vectors introduced in equation 2.29 can be seen as the generalization on the sphere of the MSFs expressed by Hermite polynomials solving the LRSW problem on the beta-plane. In this sense, they can be sorted in a similar fashion, so that the first Hough function is symmetrical around the equator, and never crosses the zero, the second one is anti-symmetrical and crosses once the zero line, the third one is again symmetrical and crosses the zero line twice, and so on. In particular, the very first Hough vectors describe modes primarily occupying the tropical region.

For each zonal wavenumber k , 3DNMs can be sorted along the meridional wavenumber n , which descends from the separation stated in equation 2.28. Hough harmonics achieve an automatic separation into two modes type, called oscillations of the first and second kind (Kasahara 2020), to be seen as generalization on the sphere respectively of IG and RW modes (Kasahara 2020; Matsuno 1966) found on the beta-plane.

The KW is also present in 3DNM as the slowest eastward propagating mode, and corresponds to the generalization on the spherical domain of the solution derived for the same problem on the equatorial beta-plane Matsuno (1966).

2.2.3. 3DNM KWs

Figure 2.2 shows the wind and height fields for the $k = 1$ KW, equivalent depth $D_m = 203$ m in 3DNM representation, as solved by MODES. The defined KW is dominated by the zonal wind component, with a meridionally symmetrical field peaking on the equator; its meridional wind component is comparatively tiny and anti-symmetrical (Žagar et al. 2015a). For what concerns the height field, this is generally large and symmetrical, in phase with the zonal wind field.

Figure 2.1.: Dispersion diagram for the LRSW solutions on the equatorial beta-plane. Shown modes are $n = 1, 2$ eastward and westward IG (EIG, WIG), equatorial RW (ER), MRG and KW. Shaded areas include equivalent depths between 8 m (solid) and 90 m (dashed). Figure from Knippertz et al. (2022) .

Figure 2.2.: KW $k = 1$ mode, $D_m = 203$ m. From MODES (2022) .

Stratospheric KWs

The first striking feature of perturbation energy spectra of KWs extracted with 3D normal-mode filtering, is that variance peaks at modes with equivalent depth around 450 m, which gives a propagation speed around 60 m/s in dry conditions (Žagar et al. 2016). This depicts quite of a distant picture from the slowly propagating CCEWs introduced *supra*, and can be seen as a ‘dry’ regime of fast-propagating, stratospheric KWs.

These faster-propagating modes can be described as internal gravity waves whose horizontal features can reach, in the tropics, planetary scales. These modes define stratospheric KWs propagating in response to a diabatic source with typical scale-length spanning the troposphere (Stephan et al. 2021).

Vertical profiles

As already mentioned *supra*, there are several methods currently used by researchers for the identification of equatorial waves, and a detailed comparison can be found in Knippertz et al. (2022) . It is here worth pointing out at the meaning of D_m in 3DNM decomposition with respect to those based on frequency filtering, such as FWF used by Wheeler and Kiladis (1999) .

Frequency filtering is generally based on a Fourier transformation in longitude and time of the chosen tropical fields. The location of the obtained coefficients on the dispersion diagram then allows the identification of the specific wave type and mode. Simultaneously, these properties define the observed equivalent depths for the signal.

3DNM decomposition is instead an intrinsically static method, and contains no information in the time/frequency domain. Equivalent depths are determined by the projection of the Hough coefficients onto each VSF. In order to interpret the meaning of equivalent depths in the 3D-NM setting, one must therefore refer to the shape of the VSFs themselves.

Vertical structures in brief

The vertical coordinate σ is typically a discretized value into a number of levels N between 0 and 1. The number of levels N is the vertical resolution of the deployed grid; in the case of ECMWF HRES model, there are $N = 137$ vertical levels, spanning from the surface of the Earth to above the stratopause. By consequence, solving the vertical problem yields N VSFs and N equivalent depths D_m .

As the resolution increases, the VSFs and their eigenvalues D_m progressively converge, approaching the limit set of eigensolutions for the problem. Žagar et al. (2022) show that the highest modes (with small equivalent depths) are the last one to converge; instead, for the first 20 modes the dependency on N is considered small already above $N = 43$ layers, so that they can be already considered good approximation of the limit eigensolutions of the problem.

VSFs $m = 1, \dots, 4$ are barotropic in the tropical troposphere, while modes $m = 5, \dots, 12$ span a first baroclinic structure. Investigation using 3D-NM filtering on a 40-years long ERA5 dataset showed that most KW climatological mean projects on the troposphere with a first baroclinic mode (Žagar et al. 2022). This structure follows closely the theoretical description of convection-coupling mechanisms found in literature and mentioned *supra*.

Equivalent depths An insight on the meaning of equivalent depth is key to understand open issues on CCEWs. As noted *supra*, equivalent depth is defined as the eigenvalue of the vertical structure problem defined by equation A.7, A.8 and A.9; by defining the invariant eigenvalue, one can see that equivalent depth is strongly connected to the stability parameter, so that a more stratified atmosphere is able to propagate faster gravity waves.

However, determination of the phase speed and the equivalent depth in observed fields is a nontrivial problem. During the previous discussion, we reported that two different methods, namely FWF adopted *e.g.* in Wheeler and Kiladis (1999) and 3DNM filtering used in Žagar et al. (2022), identify the peak spectral density at two different equivalent depths.

Žagar et al. (2022) show that a typical KW of equivalent depth 400 m projects, under FWF, also on the smaller 75 m and 25 m discussed *supra*. The authors argue that, due to time- and space-dependent forcing, the main KW signal appears under FWF as a superposition of frequencies. This ultimately provides equivalent depths significantly smaller than those given from linear theory.

2.2.4. Forecasts

ECMWF forecasts show reduced forecast skill in the tropics; in particular, the forecast ensemble spread of KW modes is typically smaller than the actual mode variance (Žagar et al. 2015b). In Žagar (2017) it is shown that KWs are associated to the largest tropical analysis uncertainty; which has a peak around vertical mode 13, to be associated with slow, convectively-coupled modes. Fastest error growth associated with the largest uncertainty in the analysis, is associated instead to vertical mode 4, mainly projecting on the stratosphere. Such vertical mode is also found to show a peak in spectral energy for Kelvin waves under 3DNM decomposition.

Phase correlations

KWs show a coupling between temperature, moisture and wind fields. This relationship is expressed by a close correlation in phase of the decomposed field signals.

KWs show approximately a $\pi/2$ cycle lag between temperature and velocity fluctuations (Andrews et al. 1987; Wheeler and Kiladis 1999), revealing a strong connection between winds and convective activity via temperature advection. This lag is quantified as $3\pi/8$ by Nakamura and Takayabu (2022), and can be observed similarly also

in forecast validation, when comparing precipitation and convergence fields (Dias et al. 2018).

Within this framework, wave phases are a central aspect of CCEWs descriptions and this justifies their investigation in many of the mentioned studies. In Dias et al. (2018) it is shown that global models (by ECMWF and National Weather Service, NWS) satisfactorily reproduce such phase coherence between precipitation and wind fields. However, verification of KWs forecasts show that phase forecast skills deteriorate rapidly around day 5 also at the largest synoptic scales.

2.3. Atmospheric predictability

The concept of predictability expresses the understanding that even perfect models of physical systems may be characterized by intrinsically-limited prediction skill. Predictability can be defined as the time range within which errors in forecasts are significantly smaller, *e.g.* less than 60%, than typical variability of the described physical processes.

2.3.1. Stability vs. predictability

The long-term stability along a dimension of a dynamical system can be described in terms of an exponential evolution with respect to an independent variable t , *e.g.* time:

$$A_j(t) \sim e^{\lambda_j t} \quad (2.45)$$

where A is the dynamical quantity and j a dimension of the phase space. λ_j takes the name of Lyapunov's exponent, and its values is sufficient to describe what the system's evolution look like along the dimension.

Lyapunov exponents

For negative values of λ_j , the evolution will contract over time and collapse to a static stable state (this would be the case of *e.g.* damped oscillations); if the Lyapunov exponent is zero, the system will be stable and not lose energy along that dimension (this would be the case of *e.g.* a non-dissipative pendulum).

Whenever a physical system possesses instabilities, it can be described by a larger-than-zero Lyapunov exponent (Kalnay 2003). True and forecast state can be described as initially close trajectories exponentially spreading apart with time.

This concept can be illustrated by considering a point in the phase space: its local stability can be explored with a linearization of the system's equations around it, which is indeed the computation of the local Lyapunov exponents. If all Lyapunov exponents are negative, the trajectories will tend to converge locally on the point, and this defines a stable solution of the system. If the largest Lyapunov exponent is positive, this determines exponential error growth.

Saturation of errors

Dynamical models of physical systems are subject to fairly general constraints, namely conservation of energy and mass, and geometric properties. This means that the accessible points in phase space are enclosed within some hyperbox, and trajectories must entirely lie within it (Kalnay 2003).

In other terms, when looking at a dimension of the physical system such as, *e.g.* velocity or position, a point's trajectory projected on it will never go to infinity, even if characterized by a positive Lyapunov exponent, which serves in fact only a local description of the dynamical system.

Given a generic state vector \mathbf{u} of the atmosphere, defined as a deviation of the true state from the climatological mean, the climatological covariance \mathbf{U} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{U} \equiv \overline{\mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{u}} \quad (2.46)$$

where the overlying bar denotes a time average over a long time period.

Given a deterministic forecast $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$, the error covariance is given by (Kalnay 2003):

$$\overline{(\hat{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{u})^T (\hat{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{u})} = \overline{\hat{\mathbf{u}}^T \hat{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{u} - \hat{\mathbf{u}}^T \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}^T \hat{\mathbf{u}}} \rightarrow 2\mathbf{U} \quad (2.47)$$

where it is assumed that the model reproduces the correct climatological covariance and that forecast and true state become decorrelated after finite time due to loss of forecast skill. Taking the squared root of the field covariance yields the root mean squared errors (RMSE), that are bound to saturate $\sqrt{2\mathbf{U}}$. This reflects the fact that RMSE by definition provide describe forecast errors as closely related to the second momentum of their underlying statistical distribution.

2.3.2. Facets of predictability

Exponential error growth implies that a sensitive increase in predictability can be achieved only by a massive increase in the precision of the initial state. *e.g.*, for a doubling time of errors of approximately 2 days as estimated in Lorenz (1982) for a perfect atmospheric model, initial errors must be reduced by a factor ten, to increase predictability by 8 days.

At this point, two important aspects of predictability have to be considered. The first one concerns the accuracy of this concept to describe local conditions of the system, in space and time. The second one deals with the practical forecast conditions, where imperfect models are deployed.

Flow dependence

Atmospheric predictability shows indeed a day-to-day variability (Kalnay 2003) in space and time: on some days and regions forecast may prove very accurate for weeks, on some other may fail even on the shortest time ranges. The fundamental notion that the

atmosphere must have some intrinsic predictability, as introduced in Lorenz (1969), is therefore an average description of the system. The local description is more articulated.

The fundamental reason for variability of predictability in space and time responds to the multiplicity of attractors and instabilities occurring in an extended complex system with many dimensions and is expressed by the concept of flow dependence of predictability.

Flow dependence can be brutally stated as a fundamental correlation between the state of the system and forecast errors. At a given point in time and space, if the atmosphere is *e.g.* in a state very close to the onset of a physical instability, according to what said *supra* predictability is expected to be reduced.

Instabilities are also characterized by an extended range of space scales, and typically small instabilities generally tend to grow faster. This sets another character of flow dependence, which is related to the typical scales of instability at specific regions.

Mid-latitudes instabilities are known to be dominated by baroclinic instabilities at synoptic scale; however these are typically negligible in the tropics, where instead barotropic and convective instabilities dominate the system (Kalnay 2003).

Practical predictability

Numerical weather prediction (NWP) models are in a certain sense the best knowledge available of the atmosphere as a physical system, despite being an imperfect description of it. The impact of model deficiencies on predictability sets a distinction between the concept of intrinsic predictability, introduced *supra*, and one of practical predictability.

This distinction stems from the work presented in Lorenz (1969), where the author refined the previously introduced concept of doubling time or errors. On the one side, intrinsic predictability defines the extent to which the atmosphere can be predicted under ideal modeling and observational conditions; on the other side, practical predictability describes the predictive potential under currently available procedures (Melhauser and Zhang 2012).

Model errors In Reynolds et al. (1994) was introduced a description for forecast errors growth characterized by a linear increase of errors introduced by the model and exponential amplification of the initial ones. Following Kalnay (2003), this is expressed by the following formula:

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = (bv - s)(1 - v) \quad (2.48)$$

where v is the normalized variance of random error, b stands for the growth rate of initial errors, and s is the growth due to model deficiencies.

Figure 2.3.: Error growth as given by formula 2.48 with parameters estimated for the tropics and middle-latitudes.

Forecasts in the tropics

The two error growth parameters were then estimated by Reynolds et al. (1994) from historical model outputs separately for the middle-latitudes and the tropics. The doubling time of initial errors was estimated around 2.5 days for the middle-latitudes and around 10 days for the tropics. As concerns instead the error growth due to model deficiencies, it was estimated to be 0.05 per day in the middle-latitudes and 0.1 per day in the tropics. Figure 2.3 shows graphically the curves according to formula 2.48 for the estimated parameters in the tropics and middle-latitudes.

This description shows two very different scenarios for model performances. Model errors in the tropics have primarily been associated to imperfect convection simulation. In fact, in order to simulate these sub-grid scale processes, NWP models have historically resorted to their parametrization, especially for convection (see *e.g.* Kalnay (2003)).

However, whether simulated convection constitutes the limiting factor to practical predictability in the tropics, is still an open question. In Mapes et al. (2008) a high-resolution mode model with explicit convective simulation at cloud system scale was used to explore factors of limited tropical predictability. From results, the authors were not able to draw any conclusion on whether this is attributed to ‘tropical chaos’ or dynamical interactions between tropics and extra-tropics.

On the shortest ranges of predictions (up to 2-3 days) errors mostly reflect uncertainties in the initial state, the analysis. Accuracy of the analysis is given not only by the accuracy and amount of observations, but also by spatio-temporal correlations that characterize the system. In particular, geostrophic adjustment constitutes a fundamental balance relationship for analysis at the middle-latitudes (Žagar et al. 2005). Its impact in the tropics instead, where Coriolis force is close to zero, is significantly smaller.

Modern models estimate forecast uncertainties by running ensemble simulations, where each member of the ensemble starts from a slightly perturbed initial state (see *e.g.* Kalnay

(2003)). Within this setting, the spread between the runs is meant to provide an estimate of the time-dependent statistical distribution of errors. ECMWF operational ensemble indicate that largest initial uncertainties are in the tropical upper troposphere (Žagar 2017). Moreover, Žagar et al. (2015) had also shown that in the tropics ensembles tended to have a smaller spread than the error of the ensemble mean. These findings seemingly indicate deficiencies in ECMWF simulated convection, affecting both the accuracy of the initial state and the short-range forecast.

2.3.3. What are forecast errors

In practical forecast evaluation settings, several metrics have been introduced over time, gradually reflecting specific needs related to the improvement of operational NWP models (see Gilleland et al. (2009) for an overview). A main distinction can be traced between systematic and random errors, namely attributed to bias and root mean squared-error (RMSE) metrics.

Systematic and random

The presentation given *supra* of the theoretical framework for error growth and saturation, assumed forecasts to be unbiased. This property refers to a specific condition of the first statistical momentum of errors to be zero. Let \mathbf{x}^T and \mathbf{x} respectively the true and forecast state of a system. Error e can be defined as the difference between the two:

$$e \equiv \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^T \quad (2.49)$$

so that the temporal average of e is given by the difference in climatological means of the true and predicted state, and is given the name of bias:

$$\bar{e} = \bar{\mathbf{x}} - \overline{\mathbf{x}^T} \quad (2.50)$$

Bias describes the systematic difference between predicted and true state and is associated with the inability of real models to completely catch the mean observed state (Jolliffe and Stephenson 2011).

In practical settings, the initial state of the model is constrained by observations, so that \bar{e} typically is a function of forecast length, and its evolution expresses a drift of the model toward states less and less correlated to observations. This systematic difference between forecasts and observations constitute a measure incorporating systematic errors in both observations and model.

The deviation of e from its mean value, can be formally attributed to a random component e' :

$$e = \bar{e} + e' \quad (2.51)$$

whose temporal mean is by definition zero. A traditional and widely used way to evalu-

ate errors is given by root-mean-squared error (RMSE metrics:

$$RMSE_{typ} \equiv \sqrt{e^2} \quad (2.52)$$

which is in essence a non-centered biased second statistical momentum for e . This has been indicated as $RMSE_{typ}$ because in this work RMSE refers instead to a centered version of the statistics. This is done to account random contributions coming from e' separately from systematic errors:

$$RMSE \equiv \sqrt{\overline{(e')^2}} \quad (2.53)$$

Formally, the mean squared error MSE is:

$$MSE = RMSE^2 = \overline{(e')^2} = \overline{(x - \bar{x})^2} + \overline{(x^T - \bar{x}^T)^2} - 2\overline{(x - \bar{x})(x^T - \bar{x}^T)} \quad (2.54)$$

so that, for long forecast, due the decorrelation between x and x^T , MSE saturate to the sum of the forecast and observed variance. These variances can have significantly different values in practical NWP settings.

Beyond RMSE

While forecast verification aims at measuring whether the forecast shows realistic or at least plausible structures, metrics such as RMSE incorporate just a specific operational procedure to this purpose. In particular Jolliffe and Stephenson (2011) point out that these metrics implicitly assume as a target for NWP to approach perfect forecasts. However, this assumption became over time less and less substantiated as NWP models incorporated increasingly fine spatial scales, up to scales considered theoretically unpredictable (Jolliffe and Stephenson 2011).

More complex verification approaches have been initially introduced for the verification of spatial structures such as, *e.g.* thunderstorms. Within this setting, increased resolution can easily lead to a decline in skills evaluated with RMSE if the structure is predicted, but displaced from the observed one. This generally leads to a double penalization, given by a missed prediction on one grid-point, and a false alarm in the one nearby.

For this reason, in a study by Hoffman et al. (1995) errors associated to spatial structures have been decomposed into several components. These were distortion, displacement, amplitude and finally a residual part. Each of these component would incorporate the 'nature and degree if spatial manipulation necessary to achieve congruence'. Along this line Buschow (2022) used wavelets to describe displacement as phase errors for rainfall forecasts.

While these approaches primarily referred to small-scale precipitation and thunderstorm structures, there are to our knowledge no studies investigating displacement errors at synoptic and planetary scales, besides one by Dias et al. (2018) . In that study,

precipitation forecasts have been verified for different equatorial waves, assessing also predictability in phase for the large $k > 16$ scales.

Filtering is typically considered a separate class of spatial verification techniques (Gilleland et al. 2009). In fact, representations in the dual space of wave-numbers (Fourier-like) are able to catch features in a scale-dependent perspective. By sacrificing explicit localization, properties such as predictability can be investigated in terms of typical scale lengths, (see *e.g.* Buizza and Leutbecher (2015) or Žagar et al. (2017)).

More specifically, filtering using 3DNM representation provides separation into physically meaningful structures along the meridional direction. This has been used by Žagar et al. (2021) to investigate the impact on ECMWF analysis and forecast uncertainty of KW by the improved observations of zonal wind profiles provided by the European Space Agency mission Aeolus.

3. Methods

This chapter lays out the methodology used for this work. It is articulated in three sections, one describing the datasets, and two addressing each a specific research question.

3.1. Data description

For this work, fundamentally two groups of fields have been used: one for the KW and one for the OLR signal. Each group of field includes a dataset of daily forecast from ECMWF deterministic runs and a dataset used for validation, the analysis fields for the KW and observations for OLR. Both groups span a period of roughly 3 years between 2019 and 2022.

3.1.1. Kelvin Wave fields

Within the research group of Atmospheric Dynamics and Predictability at the Meteorology Institute of the University of Hamburg, 3D modal decomposition has been applied to ECMWF operational HRES forecasts.

ECMWF Operational Forecasts

HRES is a single-run deterministic model of the global atmosphere coupled with an Ocean Wave and Dynamic model, providing every day at 00UTC and 12UTC the analysis resulting from observations assimilation and 10 days forecasts. HRES uses the highest available resolution at ECMWF, currently about 9 km, and provides as an output a wide range of dynamical, thermodynamical and physical variables (ECMWF 2021). The lower resolution counterpart of HRES is the ensemble forecasting system (ENS) an ensemble of forecast runs currently at about 10 km resolution, which consists of a control unperturbed and 50 perturbed members, essential to provide estimate of forecast uncertainties.

The dataset including analysis and forecasts covers the period from September, 6 2019 to September, 2 2022, summing up to 1095 days. Fields on April, 19 2020 are corrupted and this reduced by 1 the number of available data for the MAM season; this also affects complete forecast verification on two dates during the period from April, 10 2022 to April, 30 2022 depending on the forecast lead time. The number of available dates by season is:

- **DJF:** 271 days;
 - **MAM:** 276 days;
-

- JJA: 276 days;
- SON: 272 days;

Decomposed fields

MODES is a piece of software that implements 3DNM decomposition as formulated by Kasahara and Puri (1981). It has been developed by researchers at the University of Ljubljana and its characteristics, together with an application to ERA5 reanalysis dataset presented in Žagar et al. (2015). The vertical structure functions are computed as eigen-solutions of a separate Sturm-Liouville problem (see A), providing also an equivalent depth associated to each vertical mode. The meridional structures are the Hough eigenfunctions solutions of the meridional structure problem, while the zonal decomposition is substantially a Fourier transform.

Every analysis or forecast is made up of three complex fields each for balanced, eastward and westward inertio-gravity modes; for each mode category, are stored coefficients relative to the first 200 zonal wave-numbers, 70 meridional and 70 vertical modes.

For this work, only the first 80 zonal coefficients are deployed, so that the spectral coefficients of the KW for each analysis or forecast are given by only 80 zonal wave-numbers and 70 vertical modes. The same fields transformed into physical space are on 512×256 Gaussian grids with 134 vertical levels.

Defining Kelvin Waves

Within MODES implementation of 3DNM decomposition, the KW spectral coefficients are those with meridional mode 0 within the set of eastward propagating waves.

Generally speaking, the first meridional mode mainly projects on the tropics, in a symmetrical fashion around the equator. For the KW, its meridional scale length can be approximated by the equatorial Rossby deformation radius on the β plane:

$$R_{eq} \equiv \sqrt{\frac{gD}{\beta}} \quad (3.1)$$

so that the smaller the equivalent depth of the mode, the narrower the meridional profile. For an equivalent depth around 9 km, which corresponds to the first (barotropic) mode in the deployed decomposition, the profile extends well into the middle-latitudes up to 60° ; for equivalent depths smaller than 300 m, the meridional profile is considered mostly confined in the tropics (MODES 2022).

Under such a definition, the KW is intrinsically a 3D structure; however, its meridional properties are given by only one structure function for each equivalent depth. From this descends that the meridional structure of the KW provides information only about the meridional extent, but does not effectively add new features with respect to the amplitude at the equator. In this sense, the KW in physical fields can be considered as essen-

tially flat, and is in this work treated as the average KW signal between latitudes 15°N and 15°S. This simplification is welcome since it abates computational and storage cost¹ with very little information loss.

3.1.2. Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) fields

This dataset consists of two components. The first one are daily NOAA’s CDR OLR observations. The second one are the forecast top net thermal radiation (TTR) fields extracted for the ECMWF operational deterministic output.

The dataset including both observations and forecasts for the OLR fields covers the period between January, 1 2019 and December, 31 2021 summing up to 1105 dates. Divided by season there are:

- **DJF**: 280 days;
- **MAM**: 276 days;
- **JJA**: 276 days;
- **SON**: 273 days;

OLR forecasts

Thermal, terrestrial or long-wave radiation is defined in the ECMWF operational model as that emitted or absorbed by surface, gases, clouds or particles in the atmosphere; by consequence, thermal radiation is typically characterized by longer wavelengths (4 – 100 μm) than *solar or short-wave* (0.2 – 4 μm) radiation (Hogan 2015). Given that the only non-negligible incoming radiation source in the ECMWF model is the Sun, TTR is by definition the negative integral of outgoing long-wave radiation:

$$\text{TTR}^d \equiv - \int_0^d \text{OLR}(t) dt \quad (3.2)$$

where d is the forecast day and $\text{TTR}^0 = 0$ is the starting value of the model run.

NOAA observations and verification

Forecast TTR is verified against NOAA’s observed daily OLR (Lee and NOAA CDR Program 2014). The daily dataset is obtained by calibration, blending and temporal integration of measurements performed by the High-resolution Infrared Radiation Sounders sensors mounted on satellites at use by NOAA. Data are on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid and claims an accuracy of 2 W/m^2 within a 2 W/m^2 bias when verified against operational monthly data (see Lee (2014)).

¹The meridional structure in physical space between latitudes 15°N and 15°S takes in principle 86 grid points in our datasets. In this case flattened fields are 86 times smaller than those keeping the entire meridional structure within the tropical stripe.

In order to verify forecast TTR against observations, the daily forecast OLR for every forecast day is computed as:

$$\text{OLR}^d = -(\text{TTR}^d - \text{TTR}^{(d-1)}) \quad d = 1, \dots, 10 \quad (3.3)$$

and re-gridded to the 360×180 Gaussian grid via bilinear interpolation using Climate Data Operators. Formally, OLR^d is a mean daily value and is given conventionally given a time indication corresponding to $d - 12$ h, which is the center of the period over which the mean is considered; for example, $\text{OLR}^{d=1}$ indicates the mean daily OLR centered on time 12 h after the analysis is produced.

3.2. Putting KW and OLR errors in relation

This section deals with the method used to tackle first research question, asking about the possibility to trace a connection between errors in KW-filtered forecasts and errors in OLR forecasts. This is done by looking for ‘footprints’ in the OLR observation and forecast fields and subsequently try and understand whether they are reflected in KW forecast errors, and to what extent.

3.2.1. Building relations

As discussed *supra*, KWs are often described as propagators of dynamical fields perturbations due to convective activity. Convection constitutes thereby a forcing for KW, and this substantiates the inquire on whether errors in convection simulated by the model reflect on KW forecasts.

Challenges

A first challenge when relating OLR and KW fields is given by their essential nature as 2D fields. OLR is frequently used in literature as a proxy for deep tropical convection; however, it offers scant information on the vertical profile, and provides essentially flat horizontal information. For what concerns the KW, we stated *supra* that provides essentially 2D information along the vertical direction.

Coming to the OLR and KW relation, the main problem is therefore to connect two 2D fields, one horizontal and the other vertical. In order to do this we necessarily resort to the theory of CCEWs, so that low values of OLR indicate deep convection and large cloud formation in the upper troposphere. In dynamical fields, deep convection is reflected by a convergence in winds in the lower troposphere and a divergent structure close to the tropopause, which we call here a first baroclinic structure.

A further simplification can be achieved by keeping only one of the dynamical fields of the physical KW, the zonal wind. The reason for discarding the meridional wind v is

given by the fact that is almost zero everywhere. The KW height field instead, is informative indeed, but it fundamentally reflects the amplitudes in the zonal wind field.

Furthermore, such description of convection provided *supra* essentially requires the height and wind signal to be out of phase; since this cannot be done by the 3DNM KW, we argue that such convective signal primarily projects on the zonal wind and not on the height field; the overall out-of-phase picture is obtained when also equatorial RW modes are included, eventually coming to partly cancel out the KW signal in height fields.

The OLR footprints

The approach followed for this research question consists in collecting from the OLR fields some ‘footprints’, *i.e.* recognizable planetary- and synoptic -scale pattern that can be related to convection.

When possible, we use the term ‘wet’ to refer to negative deviations in the OLR signal, and ‘dry’ in the opposite case. This is a terminological stretch, since convection does not necessarily strictly reflect precipitation data, that are not part of the datasets used for this work. However within this simplified setting we borrow these terms to build some straightforward terminology. A justification of this come also from the familiarity between OLR and precipitation data, also within the equatorial waves settings (see *e.g.* Dias et al. (2018)).

Using 3DNM decomposition to perform forecast validation requires the definition of metrics that allow to exploit the potential of such tool. In particular, we want to focus on the ability to separate amplitude and phase information from the spectral coefficients.

Simple metrics?

As anticipated *supra*, the two deployed metrics are very common in the earth sciences and the most basic ones normally used in forecast validation. The first one is the climatological mean, whose error counterpart is the climatological bias; the second one is the climatological variance, which goes together with the error variance. The challenging aspects mostly concern the interpretation of such, even simple, metrics in the KW signal.

On the one hand, this is due to the complexity associated to tropical tropospheric dynamics at small equivalent depths, that still remains to be clarified (Žagar et al. 2022), and that is largely incorporated in the KW fields.

On the other hand, this is due to the specific method for the identification of equatorial waves, showing fundamental differences from, *e.g.*, FWF techniques, to which reference is largely made in most studies on the KW mentioned *supra* (see Knippertz et al. (2022)); this requires therefore to proceed with caution and make some sense of the filtered KW fields themselves.

In particular, it is essential to clarify the meaning of the mean and bias fields, mathematically reflecting a stationary wave behaviour, and the information carried at the different vertical modes ranges both by the mean KW and its variability.

3.2.2. Metrics

Here are defined the quantities computed on fields in order to investigate systematic and random forecast errors.

The first are dealt with by computing means over time, while the latter are caught in terms of variances or standard deviations over time. Before defining the metrics, we provide in a first subsection a justification to our decision to compute these metrics only as subseasonal quantities, despite the consequent drastic reduction in sample sizes for each of these metrics.

Dataset splitting by seasons

Figure 3.1 shows the signal standard deviation for OLR and KW zonal wind in observation and analysis fields computed over the entire available period. It is possible to appreciate the correspondence in the two fields of the area of peak variance above the Indian Ocean.

Focusing on the horizontal figure for OLR, it displays compellingly bifurcated features, north and south of the equator, over the American and African continents and the Pacific. The wide area spanning from Indian Continent, through the Maritime Continent and Western Pacific is interested by large values of standard deviation throughout the entire $15^{\circ}\text{N} - 15^{\circ}\text{S}$ tropical belt.

This is a reflection of a strong seasonality in data, with largest signal intensities during the winter/summer seasons and significant meridional excursion given by the ITCZ sweeping over continents. Such strong seasonality can also be appreciated in the KW signal (see *e.g.* figure 4.11) and displays all the fragility of an approach aiming at maximizing the sample size and considering all dates as elements coming from the same population; in the opposite case, dividing data by month would result in samples of roughly 90 elements. The compromise taken for this work is given by splitting datasets into seasons, thereby working on samples of roughly 270 elements.

Means

Temporal averages are used to define, for each season, mean signals and systematic errors (bias).

Mean fields The climatological mean of a variable u is typically defined as the expectation value of its observed statistical distribution, and is commonly defined practically as a 30-year average. In this sense, the mean is the best estimator on the available time of observations of the climatology. However, in this study averaged values are explored only to the extent of available datasets, therefore the terms climatology and (temporal) mean are used interchangeably. A climatology of the KW is therefore here defined for the analysis field and for each forecast lead time and depicts the mean observed signal in

Figure 3.1.: Standard deviation of KW zonal wind (top) and OLR (bottom) signals respectively for the analysis and the observation fields, computed for the entire available period of the datasets.

fields. The mean subseasonal signal for a generic vector quantity x is defined as:

$$\bar{x}_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi, z) \equiv \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{t \in s} x_l(\lambda, \phi, z, t) \quad (3.4)$$

where s indicates one of the seasons DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, corresponding to the boreal winter, spring, summer and autumn and the expression $t \in s$ stands for all dates in the dataset corresponding to a given season s , whose total is given by N_s . The subscript l indicates the lead time, and can be explicitly 0 for the verifying field or a value between 1 and 10 days for the forecasts to The mean signal is the best approximation given by the dataset to the subseasonal climatological mean of the quantity x . T

Bias or systematic error In principle, the bias is defined as difference in the climatological mean between the forecast and verifying field. For this work we apply the same definition, and in regime of error evaluation, this is the concurrent result of systematic errors both in observations and model discrepancies. Moreover, when verification is performed against the analyses, it is fundamental to recall that these are the result of an assimilation of observations starting from a background state, which is again the output of the model at a previous time-step.

A forecast for a given quantity x is said unbiased if the expectation value for the stochastic variable x_l is the same of the true state (Kalnay 2003). When using the analysis (or observations) as verification fields, the bias can be defined as the difference in the expected value of x between the forecast x_l and the analysis (or observations) x_0 . Therefore, the subseasonal bias, or systematic error, is defined by the following:

$$\mathbf{b}_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) \equiv \bar{x}_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) - \bar{x}_{0,s}(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) \quad (3.5)$$

with the same notation used in definition 3.4.

Means and bias in spectral space Definitions 3.4 and 3.5 for the subseasonal mean and bias can be straightforwardly applied also to spectral coefficients due to the linearity of both the mean and the 3DNM transformations:

$$\mathbf{b}_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) = \mathcal{D}_m \bar{\mathbf{b}}_m^k \mathbf{H}_m^k(\lambda, \phi) G_m(\sigma) = \begin{pmatrix} b_u \\ b_v \\ b_h \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \overline{u_{l,s}} - \overline{u_{0,s}} \\ \overline{v_{l,s}} - \overline{v_{0,s}} \\ \overline{h_{l,s}} - \overline{h_{0,s}} \end{pmatrix} (\lambda, \phi, \sigma) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{b}}_m^k \equiv (\overline{\chi_{l,s}})_m^k - (\overline{\chi_{0,s}})_m^k \quad (3.7)$$

So that $\bar{\mathbf{b}}_m^k$ expresses the bias in spectral space.

Of special interest is the possibility to back-transform into physical space only a certain

set of vertical modes:

$$\mathcal{D}_m (\bar{\chi}_{l,s})_m^k \mathbf{H}_m^k(\lambda, \phi) G_m(\sigma) = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{u}_{l,s} \\ \bar{v}_{l,s} \\ \bar{h}_{l,s} \end{pmatrix}^\ddagger (\lambda, \phi, \sigma) \quad m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (3.8)$$

where \mathcal{M} indicates a specific subset of vertical modes and the superscript symbol \ddagger the corresponding physical field.

Variability

A first-order description of the variability of a population with respect to a mean value is formally given by the centered second moment statistics, or variance. Such quantity provides information on the interval around the mean within which most of the occurrences from a given population are expected to be found. The squared root of the variance has the same dimension of the quantity it describes, and is the one that is used throughout the work.

RMSE Root mean squared deviation (RMSE) from the subseasonal mean is used to describe subseasonal variability in the dataset. RMSE for a generic vector quantity x is defined as:

$$\text{RMSE}(x)_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi, z) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{t \in s} (x_l(\lambda, \phi, z, t) - \bar{x}_l(\lambda, \phi, z))^2} \quad (3.9)$$

following the same notation as *supra*. RMSE constitutes the best estimate of the subseasonal climatological variability that can be given by the dataset.

RMSE Root mean squared errors (RMSE) for this work are defined in a totally similar way as subseasonal quantities on the differences between forecasts and verifying fields:

$$\text{RMSE}(x)_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi, z) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{t \in s} (e_l(\lambda, \phi, z, t) - \bar{e}_l(\lambda, \phi, z))^2} \quad (3.10)$$

$$e_l(\lambda, \phi, z, t) \equiv x_l(\lambda, \phi, z, t) - x_0(\lambda, \phi, z, t) \quad (3.11)$$

in a totally analogous way as definition 3.9. We point out that RMSE is totally blind to the systematic part of subseasonal errors, and reflects the amplitude of random errors.

RMSD and RMSE in spectral space RMSD and RMSE can be defined in spectral space in a totally similar way:

$$(\text{RMSD}_{l,s})_m^k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{t \in s} (\mathcal{D}_m(\chi_l)_m^k(t) - (\overline{\chi_{l,s}})_m^k)^2} \quad (3.12)$$

$$(\text{RMSE}_{l,s})_m^k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{t \in s} (\mathcal{D}_m(e_l)_m^k(t) - (\overline{e_{l,s}})_m^k)^2} \quad (3.13)$$

$$(e_l)_m^k(t) = (\chi_l)_m^k(t) - (\chi_0)_m^k(t) \quad (3.14)$$

Since RMSD and RMSE are non linear operators, they do not commute with any of the transformations involved in 3DNM projection. This means that transforming RMSD computed on physical space does not give RMSD in modal space and viceversa. However, if all indices of $(\text{RMSD}_{l,s})_m^k$ are contracted, it is straightforward to see that the total combined variance induced by the norm 2.33 coincides in spectral and physical space as a consequence of Parseval's theorem:

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{MSD}_{l,s}) &\equiv (\text{RMSD}_{l,s})_m^k (\text{RMSD}_{l,s})_m^k = \frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{t \in s} \sum_{k,m} \left(\mathcal{D}_m(\chi_l)_m^k(t) - (\overline{\chi_{l,s}})_m^k \right)^2 = \\ &= \frac{1}{N_s - 1} \sum_{t \in s} (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

where identity 2.33 for the inner product has been used.

Relative Errors

Relative errors are defined by normalizing RMSE with RMSD at a given lead time \tilde{l} :

$$\frac{\text{RMSE}(\mathbf{x})_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi)}{\text{RMSD}(\mathbf{x})_{\tilde{l},s}(\lambda, \phi)} \quad (3.16)$$

Relative errors are by definition dimensionless and are computed in order to evaluate the magnitude of the errors with respect to their theoretical saturation value. For unbiased forecasts, as seen *supra*, relative errors are constrained in the domain $[0, \sqrt{2}]$.

For a forecast day, a first-order guess is given by the mean state over the studied period and its accuracy at each point by the standard deviation (defined *supra* as RMSD). In order to provide a meaning to relative errors, we make the rough assumption that point-wise values and errors are Gaussian-distributed. If the relative error is 0.6, this means that the error standard deviation σ_e is 0.6 times the standard deviation from the mean σ ; this means that, under this simplified assumption, while $\sim 68\%$ of forecasts are expected to be within $\pm 1\sigma_e$ from the forecast, $\sim 45\%$ of them are expected to be within the same interval from the subseasonal mean. A rough definition of performance can be given as the ratio of forecasts falling within the $\pm 1\sigma_e$ interval from the forecast and those falling within the same interval centered on the subseasonal mean. With such definition a relative error of

0.6 means that forecasts offer roughly 50% more accuracy than the bare mean. The value 0.6 for relative errors is here taken as a reference threshold for evaluating short-time (< 5 days) predictability.

3.3. Amplitude and phase errors

This section derives a method to address the second research question, asking whether the spectral representation of the KW offered by 3DNM decomposition allows for a separation between the contribution to errors due to a displacement (or phase shift) or to magnitude misrepresentation (amplitude error).

Every field in modal space is a set of complex coefficients, as shown by equation 2.32. In the following discussion spectral numbers k and m are left implicit. We refer to the equivalence between the rectangular and polar notation for coefficients $f, a \in \mathbb{C}$

$$s = s_R + is_I \quad s_R, s_I \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.17)$$

$$s = Se^{i\sigma} \quad S \in [0, +\infty), \quad \sigma \in (-\pi, \pi] \quad (3.18)$$

$$S = \sqrt{s_R^2 + s_I^2} = \sqrt{ss^*} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\sigma = \arg s \quad (3.20)$$

where the subscripts R and I denote respectively the real and imaginary part for the rectangular complex notation; S and σ are respectively amplitude and phase of the polar complex notation. Well-known relations 3.19 and 3.20 show that the two notations are equivalent.

Similarly, we use letters f and a respectively for the spectral coefficients of a forecast and the verifying analysis:

$$f = f_R + if_I = Fe^{i\phi} \quad (3.21)$$

$$a = a_R + ia_I = Ae^{i\alpha} \quad (3.22)$$

so that the error e is given by:

$$e \equiv f - a \quad (3.23)$$

$$e_R = f_R - a_R \quad (3.24)$$

$$e_I = f_I - a_I \quad (3.25)$$

$$e = e_R + ie_I = Ee^{ie} \quad (3.26)$$

3.3.1. Distance metrics

Let the following definition for the oriented phase difference between two angles θ_1 and θ_2 :

$$\text{dist}(\theta_1, \theta_2) \equiv [(\phi - \alpha + \pi) \bmod 2\pi] - \pi \quad (3.27)$$

whose apparently complicated structure is meant to deal with the fact that phases live on a circular domain $(-\pi, \pi]$.

We define therefore the following straight differences:

$$\Delta = (F - A) \quad (3.28)$$

$$\delta = \text{dist}(\phi, \alpha) \quad (3.29)$$

respectively, the straight amplitude and oriented phase difference. This latter is the smallest angle between the forecast and the analysis vectors on the complex plane.

Pure amplitude error In the case when the forecast and verifying analysis have the same phase ($\phi = \alpha$, $\delta = 0$), the error is completely defined by the amplitude difference:

$$e = (F - A)e^{i\alpha} \quad (3.30)$$

$$\implies E = |(F - A)| = |\Delta| \quad (3.31)$$

$$\implies e^{i\epsilon} = \text{sign}(\Delta)e^{i\alpha} \quad (3.32)$$

from which one can see that the only relevant quantity for the determination of E is the straight amplitude difference Δ .

Pure phase error If forecast and verifying analysis have the same amplitude ($F = A$, $\Delta = 0$) the error is completely determined by phase difference:

$$e = A(e^{i\phi} - e^{i\alpha}) \quad (3.33)$$

$$\implies E = A\sqrt{2(1 - \cos(\phi - \alpha))} = A\sqrt{2(1 - \cos(\delta))} \quad (3.34)$$

$$\implies e^{i\epsilon} = \frac{e^{i\phi}(1 - e^{-i\delta})}{\sqrt{2(1 - \cos(\delta))}} \quad (3.35)$$

Equation 3.34 shows that, in this case, error amplitude E can get as large as 2 times the wave amplitude only due to the error in phase. This shows the well-known problem of ‘double penalization’ (Gilleland et al. 2009) when using validation methods such as RMSE.

General case For the general case, when the forecast differs from the analysis both in phase and amplitude ($\Delta \neq 0, \delta \neq 0$):

$$Ee^{i\epsilon} = Fe^{i\phi} - Ae^{i\alpha} \quad (3.36)$$

$$\implies E = \sqrt{F^2 + A^2 - 2AF \cos(\delta)} \quad (3.37)$$

$$\implies e^{i\epsilon} = \frac{e^{i\alpha}(Re^{i\delta} - 1)}{\sqrt{1 + R^2 + 2R \cos(\delta)}} \quad R \equiv \frac{F}{A} \quad (3.38)$$

Equation 3.37 shows that when straight phase difference $\delta \neq 0, E > |\Delta|$, so that in general $E \geq |\Delta|$.

3.3.2. Distribution of phases

As seen *supra*, 3DNM decomposition provides essentially static pictures. This is a fundamental difference from other methods, typically incorporating both time and space coordinates to filter the wanted dispersion relationship (see Knippertz et al. (2022)).

However, it is possible to refer to the LRSW model, where for each eigensolution is given a dispersion relation $\omega(k)$, defining the time evolution as a rotation of the corresponding coefficients on the complex plane according to the following (see MODES implementation in Žagar et al. (2015)):

$$s(t) = s(t_0) e^{-i\omega(k)(t-t_0)} \quad (3.39)$$

Let's rewrite definition 3.22 for the analysis field by introducing time dependency to represent all available analysis dates t within the available range $0, 1, \dots, t_{fin}$:

$$a(0) \equiv A(0) e^{i\alpha_0} \quad (3.40)$$

$$a(t) = A(0) e^{i\alpha(t)} \quad (3.41)$$

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 - \omega t \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, t_{fin} \quad (3.42)$$

where ω is the propagation frequency of the specific mode, as defined by the linear theory of RSW.

Uniform-distribution of phases state can be easily inferred for α from equation 3.42, whose integration over a long time-period gives immediately zero for every mode. As shown in figures 3.2a and 3.2b, this may hold true for certain modes, but not for others, that take instead the form of stationary waves.

Stationary waves Besides the neat description provided *supra*, we must deal with the fact that temporal evolution of Hough modes in the real atmosphere is typically not free. Indeed, the KW is indeed considered in the troposphere as a CCEW, *i.e.* constantly forced by convection.

This opens a question concerning to what extent uniform phase-distribution argued *supra* can be expected in the real atmosphere. One may argue that freely propagating, lower stratospheric KW can be expected to have such described uniform distribution. Instead, asymmetrical forcing and topographical features can be expected to determine a phase tuning around a specific value.

One of the first pieces of evidence for such tuning was provided by Simmons (1982), using zonally-dependent observed heating vertical profiles. These were used as forcing term for a non-linear barotropic vorticity equation model, obtaining a standing wave pattern. Like the KW, this peaked in in the tropical atmosphere with zonal wavenumber 1, extending significantly into the winter hemisphere.

A main standing KW is also be observed in reanalysis data by Žagar et al. (2022). There, the Kelvin wave climatology projects in the troposphere on a first baroclinic mode and a peak variance is found around 90E latitude. Figure 3.2b shows indeed the distribution of phases for the Kelvin wave mode $k = 1, m = 29$ in our dataset. This shows a unimodal distribution for the phase term on the circular domain, peaking somewhere around -170 deg.

3.3.3. Phase errors

All following discussion on phase errors KW errors concerns only subseasonal deviations from the mean signal for each analysis or forecast lead time. We refer to the outcome of this procedure as centered fields, here denoted with overlying \sim :

$$\tilde{\chi}_{l,s} \equiv \chi_{l,s} - \overline{\chi}_{l,s} \quad s = \text{DJF, MAM, JJA, SON} \quad (3.43)$$

where the same notation as in subsection 3.2.2 has been used. In the physical space this is equivalent to subtracting the subseasonal mean signal from each field. In modal space, this is a displacement of the barycenter of the spectral coefficients to the center of the phase space, as illustrated in figure 3.4 for a single spectral coefficient. The vectorconnecting the centers of the two original clouds is the bias in modal representation.

Every dynamical state can be represented as a collection of spectral coefficients belonging to the complex domain. As seen *supra*, the squared amplitude of the spectral coefficients is the perturbation energy associated to a specific mode. However, the complex representation provides information about the phase of a specific state, which is strictly linked to its dynamical evolution.

In the case of Kelvin waves, characterized in the LRSW model by a purely zonal and linear evolution, the evolution of phases in spectral coefficients can be interpreted in a pretty direct fashion as the zonal position of the wave phase along its propagation direction.

Here follow a discussion of two possible methods for investigating phase errors. The first one, ‘phase differences’, is based on statistics related to the distribution of δ on a

circular domain. A second one, ‘variance decomposition’, consists in decomposing the total error variance in separate contributions. Advantages and disadvantages of these methods are briefly discussed before introducing the method actually deployed in this work: ‘error separation’.

Phase differences

On short forecast lead times, we can assume forecast phase ϕ to be close in value to the verifying phase α , so that the phase difference δ is expected to have a peaked distribution around 0:

$$\delta_0 \approx 0 \quad (3.44)$$

$$R_\delta \gg 0 \quad (3.45)$$

where δ_0 indicates the preferred angle of δ for a given lead time and R_δ its mean residual length (refer to appendix for definitions of circular statistics). The inequality indicates for R_δ a value significantly larger than 0.

Figure 3.3a shows an example of peaked and unbiased distribution of δ at forecast day 1 for the KW mode $k = 1, m = 8$. As the forecast lead time increases, prediction skill is expected to be lost: this means that as α and ϕ progressively de-correlate, their difference δ approaches a uniform distribution over the entire circular domain. This is measured by:

$$R_\delta \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.46)$$

An example of fading forecast skill in phases can be seen in figure 3.3b, which shows the spreading-out of the distribution of δ at forecast day 5 for the KW mode $k = 7, m = 16$.

Phase forecast bias shall express a preferred direction β different than 0 in the phase difference δ . In a biased forecast, δ follows a peaked distribution:

$$\delta_0 \approx \beta \neq 0 \quad (3.47)$$

$$R_\delta \gg 0 \quad (3.48)$$

Therefore, in order to identify a phase bias in forecast one needs in general both quantities to be significantly different than zero. In fact, as seen supra, whenever R_δ approaches 0, the preferred direction δ_0 loses any meaning.

Generally, a value $\delta_0 > 0$ indicates a westward shift while $\delta_0 < 0$ indicates an eastward shift in forecasts. Since KW eastward propagation is a clockwise rotation of its spectral coefficients on the complex plane, the first case tells that the KW mode propagates slower in forecasts than in the verifying fields, and conversely the second case.

This approach is similar to the method used in Buschow (2022) for evaluation of displacement errors, and has the advantage to provide a clear picture in terms of the preferred direction of δ . However, this does not say anything about the actual impact on

Figure 3.2.: Phase polar diagrams for the analysis fields. Zonal mode $k = 7$ and vertical mode $m = 27$ (a), $k = 1$, $m = 29$ (b).

Figure 3.3.: Phase differences (δ) polar diagrams. Forecast day $d = 1$, zonal mode $k = 1$ and vertical mode $m = 8$ (a), $d = 5$ $k = 7$, $m = 16$ (b).

errors of such phase bias, since modes with small and large amplitudes are all considered together. In addition to that, remains an open problem how to correctly use R_δ to evaluate the significance of the statistics δ_0 .

Variance decomposition

A different approach stems from equations 3.31 and 3.37 and consists in separate total variance into different components:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E^2 &= (F^2 + A^2 - 2AF) + 2AF(1 - \cos \delta) \\
 \Rightarrow E^2 &\equiv \Delta^2 + 2A^2(1 - \cos \delta) + 2A\Delta(1 - \cos \delta) \\
 &= E_{PA}^2 + E_{PP}^2 + E_{MAP}^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.49}$$

where the subscript *PA*, *PP* and *MAP* stand for the ‘pure amplitude’, ‘pure phase’ and ‘mixed amplitude-phase’ contribution term to error variance. In a similar manner, by noting linearity of E^2 in its separated contributions, one can use 3.49 by taking the time average of each term.

The main advantage of this method is the neat and linear decomposition of exact error variance into contributes well-attributable to the phase and amplitude errors we are interested to catch. This implies a solid quantification of error variance contributions, which was not possible with the ‘phase differences’ method. In contrast, this gives no information about the direction and amount of displacement.

However, the main problem with this approach is that there is no clear indication of what the expected values of statistics such as \overline{E}_{PA}^2 , or \overline{E}_{PP}^2 should be, *e.g.* in the case of a perfect forecast. Also, it is not clear what exactly the *MAP* term represents.

One possible alternative could be computing RMSE on amplitude and phase-locked forecast; however, this would require also a theoretical framework for evaluating the covariance between amplitude and phase errors.

Error separation

While the computation of the preferred direction of δ is well-defined and is a powerful way to show directional properties, especially from the graphical standpoint, it has the main disadvantage of being completely non-dimensional.

In order to achieve a dimensional quantification of phase errors, we exploit the fact that, as noted in the preliminary discussion, straight phase errors d are typically small, so that one can in principle define a separation of errors into amplitude and phase contributions.

For a given mode, the coefficient for the analysis, $a \in \mathbb{C}$ and for the correspondent forecast $f \in \mathbb{C}$; without loss of generality, consider $a = \Re(a)^2$. In this case, let’s use the subscript 1 to indicate the error, with the general definition:

$$e_1 = (f - a) e^{-i\alpha} \quad (3.50)$$

that would in general have both non null real and imaginary parts. If one starts from a pure phase shift case:

$$F \sin(\delta) = A \sin(\delta) e_1 = \Im(e_1) \approx e \quad (3.51)$$

at this point, introducing an amplitude error, δ staying constant, would make $\Re(e_1)$ larger. However, due to the non linearity of the transformations one shall consider the

²If $\Im(a) \neq 0$, one can always apply a suitable rotation of the complex plane represented by the unitary operator $e^{-i\alpha}$.

full expression for the real and imaginary parts:

$$\Re(e_1) = F \cos(\delta) - A \approx \Delta(1 - \delta^2/2) - A\delta^2/2 \quad (3.52)$$

$$\Im(e_1) = F \sin(\delta) \approx A\delta + \Delta\delta \quad (3.53)$$

where the approximation of small angles $\delta \ll 1$ has been explicated. One can see that $\Re(e_1)$ generally becomes smaller with increasing δ at constant Δ , and that the $A\delta^2/2$ term becomes very easily dominant with small Δ . $\Im(e_1)$ is also linearly dependent from Δ ; if we assume $\Delta = x A$ with $x \ll 1$, then x controls the degree to which $\Im(e_1)$ is a faithful representation of errors induced by phase shift.

Along the same fundamental idea of identifying real and imaginary components of e with phase and amplitude contribution, one can consider a different rotation of the complex plane. Let the following transformation:

$$f \rightarrow f' = f e^{-i\rho} \quad (3.54)$$

$$a \rightarrow a' = a e^{-i\rho} \quad (3.55)$$

$$\rho \equiv \alpha + \delta/2 \quad (3.56)$$

$$e' \equiv (f' - a') = (f - a) e^{-i\rho} \quad (3.57)$$

so that the real and imaginary parts of the error are given by:

$$\Re(e') = (F - A) \cos(\delta/2) \approx \Delta(1 - \delta^2/2) \quad (3.58)$$

$$\Im(e') = (F + A) \sin(\delta/2) \approx A\delta + \Delta\delta/2 \quad (3.59)$$

where the approximation of small angles $\delta \ll 1$ has been explicated. $\Re(e')$ now depends only on Δ and is affected by phase shift to the second order of δ in the approximation $\delta \ll 1$. A slight improvement has been obtained also for $\Im(e')$, whose linear dependence from Δ is smaller by a factor 2 than in the first definition 3.52.

What makes a metrics suited depends on the purpose and the actual situation in which it is deployed. In our scenario, the investigation of phase errors in planetary scale waves deals with the idea that displacements are expected much smaller than the wavelength, so we have implicitly assumes that it is reasonable to expect at least $\delta < \pi/2$. In any case, to complete our definition of phase-amplitude separation of errors we must define the domain of validity for δ at least as small as $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$: whenever δ is out of the domain, the separation between phase and amplitude contributions to errors is not reflected anymore by definitions 3.58 and 3.59.

Is δ small? The main argument in support to the assumptions made on δ is the following: for a given amplitude of the KW spectral coefficient, the phase configuration of the complex coefficient ultimately interacts with the zonal wave functions, resulting in a zonal phase shift. Indeed, this is what happens to the wave in physical space represen-

Figure 3.4.: The centered analysis (red points) and forecast (green points) fields defined in equation 3.43. Figuratively, this can be seen as a displacement of the barycenter of the field realizations over time (the sample) toward the origin of the complex plane.

Figure 3.5.: Rotation defined by equation 3.54. Definition of the rotation angle ρ (left) and result of the applied transformation (right). One c

Figure 3.6.: The example waves $A^k(\sigma)$ and $B^k(\sigma)$. Dashed lines delimit the ISA tropopause ($\sim 216 - 56$ hPa)

tation if the spectral coefficients for a given zonal mode are rotated by a constant phase δ :

$$\chi_m^k \rightarrow \chi_m'^k = \chi_m^k e^{i\delta} \quad (3.60)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) &= \chi_m^k \Theta_m^{KW}(\phi) G_m(\sigma) e^{ik\lambda} \\ &\rightarrow \mathbf{W}'(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) = \chi_m^k \Theta_m^{KW}(\phi) G_m(\sigma) e^{ik\lambda + \delta} \\ &= \mathbf{W}((\lambda + \delta), \phi, \sigma) \end{aligned} \quad (3.61)$$

where Θ_m^{KW} is the meridional structure function for the KW. This is in general not necessarily true for the phase difference occurring between two different fields, *i.e.* the forecast and the analysis and in general, for a given k , δ is also a function of m , or the vertical coordinate. The more general case $\delta = \delta(m)$ reflects the fact that the phase shift is in general not constant in the vertical direction, and the transformation $e^{i\delta(m)}$ is more correctly a distortion in spectral space; the phase shift is therefore a special case of such transformation, given by $\partial\delta/\partial m = 0$. Let A^k an example wave for a given zonal wavenumber k whose vertical structure is described by only one non-zero coefficient in the linear combination of vertical structure functions:

$$A^k(\sigma) = \alpha_m G_m(\sigma) = \sqrt{0.99} G_3(\sigma) + \sqrt{0.01} G_4(\sigma) \quad (3.62)$$

where α_m is the m -th spectral coefficient, and the only non-zero value is $m_6 = -1$. Let now B^k another wave of the same kind:

$$B^k(\sigma) = \beta_m G_m(\sigma) = -\sqrt{0.01} G_3(\sigma) - \sqrt{0.99} G_4(\sigma) \quad (3.63)$$

The phase difference between the two waves is therefore:

$$\delta_m = \pi \quad \text{if } m = 3, 4 \quad \text{otherwise } 0 \quad (3.64)$$

Figure 3.6 shows the physical representation of waves A^k and B^k : one can see that they are quite similar throughout vertical levels below 30 hPa; effective phase shifts are very small below 100 hPa and in very far from the half-wavelength shift suggested by the computed δ . This has been possible basically by displacing the weight from one vertical mode to the next one, and constitutes what we can call a replacement effect between vicinal modes; this must make us aware that small differences in physical space may correspond to huge differences in the values of the spectral coefficients and, in particular, to extreme values of δ for a given vertical mode.

Representation switch One can deploy the same metrics for the evaluation of phase errors in the explicit physical vertical fields. This can be done by projecting the KW spectral coefficients back to physical space in the meridional and vertical directions and

define $\zeta(k, \sigma)$, which essentially constitutes the zonal Fourier transform of the KW filtered from the physical fields:

$$\zeta^k(\sigma) = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ Z \end{pmatrix}^k (\sigma) = [\chi_m^k \Theta_m^{KW}(\phi) G_m(\sigma)]^\dagger \quad (3.65)$$

where \dagger indicates the arithmetic mean across latitudes between 15N and 15S. Within this scenario, the same definitions 3.54, 3.58 and 3.59 hold, just keeping in mind that the ζ coefficients for each k are functions of σ instead of m , which implies $\delta = \delta(\sigma)$; however, if over a range of vertical levels δ is within the $[-\pi, \pi]$ domain and constant, this can be interpreted as a zonal phase shift at those levels.

Quantification Finally, we need a method to qualify and quantify the phase shift. In the free shallow-water system, the KW solution has a very precise temporal evolution defined by its linear dispersion relationship:

$$\mathbf{W}_m(\lambda, \phi, \sigma) = \chi_m^k(t) \Theta_m^{KW} G_m(\sigma) e^{ik\lambda} \quad (3.66)$$

$$\chi_m^k(t) = \chi_m^k e^{-i\phi_m^k(t)} \quad (3.67)$$

$$\phi_m^k(t) = \omega_m^k t = k\sqrt{gD_m}t \quad (3.68)$$

where $\phi_m(t)$ expresses the eastward propagation of the wave phase. The time evolution of the spectral coefficient of a free KW in the shallow-water system is a clockwise rotation in the complex plane. Analogously, a positive δ indicates that the phase of the forecast is larger than that of the analysis, therefore we say that the forecast KW lies west of the analysis, and vice-versa for the case of negative δ . We must also take into account that a rigorous definition of the phase error in this terms strictly relies on δ being small enough and we specify this in term of the constrained domain defined supra, *i.e.* $\delta \in [-\pi, \pi]$.

Therefore, we estimate the significance of the phase error metrics as the ratio between the total squared amplitude in space and time of those errors for which $\delta \in [-\pi, \pi]$ and that of all errors:

$$r_{\text{sep},m} = \frac{\sum_k \sum_t |e_m^{*k}(t)|^2}{\sum_k \sum_t |e_m^k(t)|^2} \quad (3.69)$$

$$e_m^{*k} = \begin{cases} e_m^k, & \text{if } \delta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.70)$$

In practice, r_{sep} provides a quantification of the solidity of the phase-separation procedure on the sample.

Furthermore, we want to quantify how much of the variance for which phase-amplitude separation is defined can be attributed to an error in phase or amplitude, *i.e.* the separate

contributions of the real and imaginary parts of e' according to definitions 3.58 and 3.59. We do this by computing the ratio between the real and imaginary contribution to variance:

$$r_{\text{ph},m} = \frac{\sum_k |\Im(e_m^k)|^2}{\sum_k |\Re(e_m^k)|^2 + |\Im(e_m^k)|^2} \quad (3.71)$$

Finally, we want to quantify how much of the error variance attributed to a phase shift can be identified as an eastward phase shift:

$$r_{\text{east},m} = \frac{\sum_k |\Im(e_{\text{east},m}^k)|^2}{\sum_k |\Im(e_m^k)|^2} \quad (3.72)$$

$$\Im(e_{\text{east},m}^k) = \begin{cases} \Im(e_m^k), & \text{if } < 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.73)$$

4. Results

This chapter presents the results and is divided in three sections. The first two sections are, respectively, for the OLR and KW fields in physical representations; the third section relates the KW in spectral representation. Most of results related to the first research question (relation between OLR and KW errors) are concentrated in, but not confined to, the first two sections. The second research question (separation between KW amplitude and phase errors) is totally addressed by results of the third section.

4.1. The OLR fields

This section shows results concerning the OLR forecasts in physical representation. Firstly, quantities related to the signal in fields are considered, then those related to systematic and random errors. When possible, large scale features are pinpointed as ‘footprints’ of observed and simulated convection, as comparison elements for the successive discussion of KW fields.

4.1.1. OLR signal

Here follow results related to the OLR mean signal and its variability. As a general rule, verifying observation fields are considered; forecast fields are considered whenever remarkable differences can be noticed.

Mean

Figure 4.1 shows the subseasonal mean of observed OLR signal in the tropical belt. One can recognize throughout all the year the presence of three main centers for convective activity on South America, Africa and the Maritime Continent. This establishes a set of well-known zonal circulation cells (see figure 4.2), among which is the Walker circulation over the Western Pacific, constituting a first footprint of the OLR signal.

During the boreal winter (DJF) and summer (JJA) seasons all patterns are respectively shifted south and north the equator, reflecting the latitudinal excursion of the ITCZ. Interestingly, mean OLR amplitude over South American and African continents is comparable with that over the the Maritime continent during the DJF and MAM seasons. The OLR pattern over the Maritime Continent provides the most intense signal; it is at its strongest during the JJA and SON seasons, when it extends over the Eastern Indian Ocean in correspondence to the Indian Monsoon season.

Figure 4.1.: Intraseasonal climatological mean of observed OLR, from top to bottom during the DJF, MAM, JJA and SON seasons.

Figure 4.2.: Diagram of zonal circulation decomposed into equatorial convective cells during non-ENSO conditions from Peixoto and Oort (1992).

Figure 4.3.: Subseasonal variability (RMSD) of observed OLR.

The latitudinal span of the ITCZ over land of the Maritime and South-East Asian Continents can be associated to an annual displacement of the signal peak along the NE-SW direction. The latitudinal span is approximately 30° , such that the peak centers around 120°E in the DJF season and around 90°E in the JJA season. Such displacement over the Maritime Continent constitutes another footprint of the OLR signal.

Variability

Figure 4.3 shows the subseasonal variability of the OLR observations (RMSD, see definition in section 3.2) in the tropics. The most noticeable feature of these plots is the major role played by the so-called "warm pools" of the Indian Ocean and Western Pacific in shaping, together with land areas of the Maritime Continent and South-East Asia, a wide region of intense convective activity.

Comparison of signal variability throughout the year over these regions shows a significant meridional displacement, in a similar fashion to what observed in the mean OLR signal (figure 4.1): convective activity is intensified over the Indian Continent and Indochina especially during the JJA and SON seasons, in correspondence with the Monsoons season. During the DJF season, the largest variance is found more on the Western Pacific.

Figure 4.4.: Same as figure 4.3, but for OLR at forecast day 5.

Figure 4.5.: Subseasonal bias between observations and forecast day 5 OLR. Defined are also monitoring regions from left to right over Peru/Colombia (PE), Eastern Atlantic and Western Subsaharan Africa(AT), Central and Horn of Africa (AF), Indian Ocean (IO), Maritime Continent (MC), Western Pacific (WP).

A comparison between observed and forecast OLR (see figures 4.3 and 4.4) shows that the model is generally able to reproduce with good accuracy the major large-scale features of the observed OLR. Large signal variance is observed over continental regions and follows the meridional displacement of the ITCZ. The largest signal amplitude is observed over the Indian Ocean, Maritime Continent and the Western Pacific. The model catches the significant role of continents in convection, though variability over the Pacific and Atlantic oceans is milder in forecasts than in observations. Forecasts tend to show also a larger signal variance over the Maritime Continent and Western Pacific, which can be noticed for the DJF season by direct comparison of figures 4.4 and 4.3 and which will be discussed more in detail *infra*.

4.1.2. OLR errors

Here are discussed systematic and random OLR errors in two separate subsections. Systematic errors can be interpreted in terms of ‘wet’ and ‘dry’ features and provide a number of footprints pointing at biases in the simulated convection. Random errors carry

information about local predictability and error growth in forecasts; however, only few footprints could be identified.

Systematic errors

Figure 4.5 shows the bias between observed and forecast day 5 OLR on the tropical belt. Some monitoring regions in the tropical 15°N-S belt have been defined on the map to facilitate identification of OLR footprints in forecast bias. These are all defined in the stripe 15°N-S and include a variable number of grid points, indicated between parenthesis in the following definition list:

- **IO** (Indian Ocean): 50.5°E – 95.5°E (1472)
- **MC** (Maritime Continent): 95.5°E – 150.5°E (1792)
- **WP** (Western Pacific): 150.5°W – 165.5°W (1440)
- **PE** (Peru/Colombia - America): 84.5°W – 59.5°W (832)
- **AT** (Eastern Atlantic and Western Africa): 24.5°E – 12.5°E (1216)
- **AF** (Central and Eastern Africa): 12.5°E – 50.5°E (1248)

When verified against observations, forecasts show a generalized dry bias throughout the tropics (roughly between 6 and 8 W/m², not shown), with almost negligible growth with forecast lead time. This is also verified in each region except PE (seasons DJF, MAM, SON) and AF (season SON). Besides this difference between the typical model state and the observations, no significant speculation can be made on model errors and the way they can reflect on the dynamical fields. More informative is, in this sense, the bias growth with respect to forecast day 1; since we expect the shortest available lead time to have the closest climatology to the initial state of the model, such growth reflects a climatological drift of the model.

Footprints

Figure 4.6 shows the evolution of mean OLR in forecast fields with respect to mean OLR at forecast day 1. This is given by:

$$b_{l,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi) - b_{1,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi) \quad l = 1, \dots, 10 \quad (4.1)$$

where b^{OLR} indicates the bias as defined in section 3.2. For $l = 1$ the difference is by definition zero. This quantity is partially blind to systematic differences between forecasts and observation. Instead, it stresses on the model drift throughout the entire run, starting from the forecasts more constrained to the initial state, to forecasts more closely reflecting a non-constrained model run.

Figure 4.6.: Subseasonal mean difference of OLR between forecast days 1 to 10 and forecast day 1. Values are averages over the regions shown in figure 4.5 (dashed lines) and along the tropical stripe between latitudes 15N and 15S (solid line, TO).

The average tropical climatological OLR mean is roughly conserved throughout the model evolution, so that the bias trends in specific regions tend to compensate each other. As a general fashion, we recognize that the bias drift tends to flatten after forecast day 5, so that this lead time will generally be used as a reference to evaluate bias magnitudes. We identify *infra* some footprints for the OLR bias:

Wet Peru (DJF, MAM) The most striking feature of figure 4.5 is a strong negative bias over the western half of the South American continent (PE in figure 4.5), roughly corresponding to Peru and Colombia; the bias on this region is at its strongest in the DJF and MAM season, while during the JJA and SON seasons the bias structure extends to the eastern Pacific, closely reflecting seasonal variations in the observed signal (compare with Figure 4.1). Figure 4.6 shows a significant climatological drift during the DJF, MAM and SON seasons between 3 and 7 W/m^2 .

Dry East Atlantic (DJF) The second most important feature concerns the eastern Atlantic and Western Africa (AT in figure 4.5) during the DJF season. The AT bias evolution

(see figure 4.6) shows a significant climatological drift in the DJF season and a moderate one in the SON season. When looking at the mean observed OLR (Figure 4.1) in the same region, one can recognize a similar plume-like structure extending from continental Africa to the Ocean Basin, with a maximum in OLR around the Greenwich meridian; this corresponds to the descending branch of the local Walker circulation on the Atlantic (see Schwendike et al. (2014)) and we associate this to bias suppressed convection conditions.

Wet Africa (JJA, SON) Another bias structure is identified over Central and Eastern Africa (AF in figure 4.5). The AF bias trend of the two regions is generally characterized by moderate drift in all seasons beside SON, when it displays a significant wet bias (see figure 4.6). Besides this, we notice that the AF bias during the JJA season is very similar to the one in the AT region; therefore it constitutes a footprint also in the JJA season, indicating generally wetter conditions over both regions.

India, Indonesia, Pacific The vast area spanning the Indian Ocean, Maritime Continent and Western Pacific (IO, MC and WP regions in figure 4.5) plays a main role in the tropical zonal circulation and generates the ascending branch of what is specifically called as the Walker Circulation.

The area over Indian Ocean (IO) and Indian Continent displays widespread bias over the ocean, while the bias structure over continent undergoes a significant seasonal excursion, with a sharp peak during boreal summer, in correspondence with the onset of the Monsoon season. Generally, the IO bias offers little indication about the model behaviour except for the JJA season, where it generally indicates wetter conditions in longer forecasts. The WP bias indicates a drift toward drier conditions in the DJF season, but not significant trend otherwise.

Finally the MC bias is generally leaning toward drier conditions, especially in the JJA and SON season. Putting all things together, we can expect that the center of the region of convection to be typically displaced westward. The strongest displacement can be expected in the JJA season, a smaller one during the DJF season. The SON season footprint is instead a dry bias over the MC region.

Random errors

Figure 4.7 shows the subseasonal OLR RMSE at forecast day 1 normalized by the signal standard deviation at forecast day 1 (RMSD). The shown quantity is computed as:

$$\frac{\text{RMSE}_{l,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi)}{\text{RMSD}_{1,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi)} \quad (4.2)$$

The choice of using RMSD at forecast day 1, *i.e.* computed on actual states of the model, instead of RMSD of the observations has been done to exclude artificial magnification/reduction of normalized errors entirely due to differences in the climatological variability

Figure 4.7.: Subseasonal error standard deviation of OLR at forecast day 1 normalized by corresponding signal standard deviation for day 1.

Figure 4.8.: Same as figure 4.7, but for errors at forecast day 5.

Figure 4.9.: Excess variability in OLR forecast at day 1 with respect to observations.

between the model and the observations. In fact, as shown *infra*, they can be substantial.

The earliest onset of forecast errors concerns the Eastern Atlantic and the African continent; surprisingly, at the early stages error growth over the Maritime Continent is milder, and this is observed also in the absolute fields (not shown). The magnitude of such relative errors on these regions in the DJF and MAM seasons, and on the Western Pacific for the JJA and SON seasons is around 1. This indicates that predictability threshold of 0.6 is passed already at the shortest forecast lead times in those regions

At forecast day 5 (see figure 4.8) relative errors show values close to saturation (larger than 1) on the Atlantic (all seasons), African Continent (DJF, MAM, JJA) and Western Pacific (JJA, SON). Exception made for the JJA season, predictability is generally higher and uniform over the Indian Ocean; there RMSD show a meridional displacement over the Indian Ocean (not shown) following the seasonal displacement of variability patterns (see figure 4.4).

The region of earliest relative error growth in the Eastern Pacific slightly south the equator and in the Atlantic corresponds to a region characterized by low variability in the fields (see figure 4.4). Thus, despite being close to saturation, these absolute errors are small. Over areas in the Atlantic and Pacific characterized by large variability, relative errors are typically between 0.3 and 0.5 at forecast day 1 and between 0.6 and 1.0 at forecast day 5.

A similar contextualization also holds for the American and Maritime Continent, where the largest peaks in relative errors typically corresponds to regions of low variability. This applies also to a certain extent to the African continent *e.g.* in the SON season where the complementary shape of the relative error and variability structures is particularly clear.

Footprint: errors over Africa An exception to this general idea can be noticed over the African Continent in the JJA and MAM seasons: large relative errors are found in regions with large variability. This aspect is particularly relevant because provides a way to gauge where the model forecasts struggle the most. From this we conclude that the largest contribution to forecast errors on the continent is found indeed within the 15°N-S stripe. This generally results also in large errors except, in part, for the the DJF season, when the highest variability is found south of the 10°S latitude.

Excess variability Figure 4.9 shows the excess subseasonal RMSD at forecast day 1 with respect to observations. This is defined as:

$$\text{RMSD}_{1,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi) - \text{RMSD}_{0,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi) \quad (4.3)$$

Differences in variability between forecast and observed OLR lie within 20 W/m², which represent an interval large around 40% the variability scale of the observed signal standard deviation (compare colorbar with figure 4.3).

A remarkable general feature is the overall higher signal variability of the simulated

Figure 4.10.: Excess variability in OLR forecast at day 5 with respect to forecast day 1.

OLR over all continents and following meridional displacement consistent with that of the ITCZ. This is especially evident over the Indian Continent and South-East Asia during the JJA and SON season, as well as the Maritime Continents over the DJF and MAM season.

The excess variance pattern over Western and Central/Southern Africa is inverted between the DJF and JJA seasons; this indicates in both seasons a larger climatological variability of the model than the observations over the African continent along the ITCZ, where the RMSD is larger (compare with figure 4.3) and smaller elsewhere.

Figure 4.10 shows the difference in subseasonal RMSD between forecast day 5 and 1, *i.e.*:

$$\text{RMSD}_{5,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi) - \text{RMSD}_{1,s}^{\text{OLR}}(\lambda, \phi) \quad (4.4)$$

This quantity aims at illustrating the model drift from a state more constrained by assimilated observations, *i.e.* the shortest forecast, to a more free model run.

When compared with figure 4.9, drifts in variability show many more complicated patterns; however we can recognize a generally increasing variance over the Maritime Continent in DJF and MAM seasons, displaced over South-East Asia and India in the JJA and SON seasons.

The excess standard deviation over Western Africa tends to confirm an excess standard deviation following the ITCZ movement in the JJA and SON seasons, while the patterns over Central and Southern Africa show an inversion of the trend. The drift over the South American continent shows as well a generally inverted pattern than in figure 4.9, with increasing variance over Brazil and decreasing over the Northern part of the continent.

For both the African and American Continent, excess variability shows that the model tends to produce forecasts with higher and higher variability in correspondence to those areas characterized by strongest convection (compare with figure 4.3).

Figure 4.11.: Subseasonal mean KW zonal wind in the analysis. Horizontal section of the 153 hPa model level.

4.2. The Kelvin Wave fields

This section discusses the forecast errors in the KW-filtered forecasts in physical representation. During the presentation of results, we discuss the correspondence between KW signal and the footprints related to convective activity coming from the results related to OLR forecasts.

4.2.1. KW signal

Here follow results related to the KW mean signal and its variability. As a general rule, verifying analysis fields are considered; forecast fields are considered whenever remarkable differences can be noticed.

Mean

As already mentioned *supra*, the KW is a tropical feature extending in three dimensions. However, due to its complete symmetry around the equator and the little information given by the meridional structure, we are considering it as a 2D, vertical feature, typically in terms of its zonal wind component.

Figure 4.11 shows the mean intraseasonal KW zonal wind at the 153 hPa model level for the analysis fields. Such level has been chosen to represent the tropical upper stratosphere and lower tropopause. At this level, the mean KW is throughout the year a stationary planetary wave with amplitude around 7.5 m/s. The major peaks are respectively corresponding to the crest and trough of the $k = 1$ planetary wave insisting on the Pacific ocean and on equatorial Africa and Indian Ocean. This confirms that the strongest mean KW signal is found in the tropopause layer and dominated by zonal wavenumber $k = 1$.

The vertical section on the averaged 15°N-W tropical stripe in figure 4.12 reveals a dominant first baroclinic structure, in accordance with the theory of wave-convection coupling (see *e.g.* the KW observed in Straub and Kiladis (2002)) and with the monthly climatology of the KW signal computed by Žagar et al. (2022) . The mean KW signal is mostly negligible in the middle stratosphere and gets significantly higher only in the upper stratosphere - mesosphere, above a the 2 hPa vertical level (not shown).

KW and zonal convective cells All put together, the intraseasonal mean of KW zonal wind uncannily overlaps with a ‘textbook’ description of the tropical zonal circulation cells (see, *e.g.* Holton (2004) and Schwendike et al. (2014)), as already shown *supra* (see figure 4.2). It is important to underline that the entire period covered by the dataset is characterized by persistent *La Niña* conditions. Thereby, it is reasonable to expect that during *El Niño* or transition states the picture may differ significantly.

The ascending and descending branches of the convective cells are identified by inversions in the zonal wind direction, and can be assigned accordingly to the associated

Figure 4.12.: Subseasonal mean KW zonal wind in the analysis. Vertical section of the signal average between latitudes 15N and 15S. Black dashed lines delimit the ISA tropopause ($\sim 216 - 56$ hPa). Red dashed line indicated the 153 hPa model level.

divergence or convergence in the lower part of the tropopause layer. A first, ascending branch insists on a wide region centered on the Maritime Continent around 120°E ; this, together with the descending branch in the Eastern Pacific around 90°W , delimit the properly called Walker Circulation. An ascending branch is then found on the South-American continent, and is part of a circulation cell over the Atlantic having its descending branch over West Africa, around longitude 0° . Finally, an ascending branch is present also over the African Continent, which is reflected on a weakening of the westerly wind around 60°E .

Main topographical features of the tropics have a significant impact on the mean KW signal as well as on the convective cells. These are mostly represented by the Andes, defining a neat cut in mean signal structures around latitude 80°W , and the East African ridge, setting a strong discontinuity around latitude 40°E .

Relations with OLR The mean KW and OLR signals both incorporate sound information on the zonal tropical circulation and, in accordance with what expected by the theory, relate to each other in a complementary way, as a picture with its negative. The main OLR footprint insisted on the location of the convective activity on continents and is sound with what discussed so far on the mean KW.

Moreover, it is possible to recognize the second OLR footprint, concerning the displacement of the convective center over the Maritime Continent along the NW-SE axis. In the KW, this is reflected as a zonal displacement of the main divergence peak (figure 4.11) from its easternmost location in the DJF season to the westernmost location in the JJA season.

The easterly wind signal in the lower TTL at longitudes $0^{\circ} - 90^{\circ}\text{E}$ (figure 4.12) is divided in two main lobes, due to the presence of the ascending convective branch over the African continent, latitude around 45°E , leading east of it to a weakening and, west of it, to an intensification of the easterlies.

East of longitude 90°E , corresponding to the American Continent, it is possible to notice an interruption of the main pattern of westerlies in the lower TTL. This is to be associated to the descending branch of the Walker Circulation west of the Andes and, more at the east, to an ascending convective branch over Land.

Variability

Figure 4.13 shows the vertical profile of subseasonal variability in the KW zonal wind signal, averaged in space along the tropical 15N and 15S . A peak in variance is always found in the TTL with values around 2 m/s. As a main feature, we notice that it generally becomes duller and duller as lead time increases (all seasons except JJA); this indicates that forecasts show smaller and smaller variance in the KW signal at longer forecast times, which indicates a drift in the KW climatological variability of the model.

A compelling property of the TTL peak is that it is centered around 100 hPa in the

Figure 4.13.: Vertical profile of subseasonal variability for the Kelvin wave zonal wind. Values are given for the analysis (black) and forecast lead times 1 to 10 days (from dark blue to yellow). Dashed lines delimit the ISA tropopause ($\sim 216 - 56$ hPa) and stratopause ($\sim 1.2 - 0.6$ hPa).

middle TTL, *i.e.* at significantly higher model level than the location of the peak mean signal. This is a crucial aspect of the KW, that demarcates the difference between the regime of forced, convectively coupled signal, found in the troposphere and that of the vertically propagating gravity waves in the upper TTL and stratosphere.

Intensification in wave activity in the lower stratosphere has been associated in previous studies (see Ryu et al. (2008) and Flannaghan and Fueglistaler (2013)) both to easterlies background conditions and to the increasing static stability in the upper TTL, peaking around 20 Km altitude, *i.e.* around 58 hPa model level. Vertical variability profile are, for this reason, conditioned also by QBO (Stephan et al. 2021). Given the limited time span of the dataset, we are not able here to investigate the effect of inter-annual variations of such background conditions.

The strongest peak in variability is found in the upper stratosphere and around the ISA stratopause in all seasons; such signal shows a large seasonality, and is normally confined in model levels above 2 hPa, *i.e.* gph above 40 km (ECMWF 2020). Such peak is 1.5 to 2 times stronger than the one found in the TTL and is located over the Eastern Pacific. It is probably to be attributed to the diurnal tide and to the fact that all fields are given at time 00UTC (see figure 4.20). Despite we focus in this work on the Kelvin Wave located in the vicinity of the tropopause, it is important to notice such distribution, since it contributes significantly to the total KW signal variability, in physical as well as in spectral space.

Variability peaks around 6 m/s in all seasons, and reproduces the same features found in the ERA5 dataset by Žagar et al. (2022) , where peaks are much weaker, around 15 m²/s². I am not able to explain this, but I shall point out that, by computing the vertical KW profile as an average in the 30°N-S stripe, the variability peak is around 3.5 m/s (not shown), in line with published results.

There is a remarkable annual oscillation of the peak variability in the tropopause layer, moving from around 100°E in the DJF season to around 60°E in the JJA season. Such shift spans longitudinally the Indian Ocean and has a close resemblance with the one in the OLR signal variability, whose displacement occurs more in the east, above the Maritime Continent and South-East Asia. The westward shift during the JJA season has been associated to the seasonal displacement of the easterly wind background (compare with figure 4.11), an amplification factor for of the KW signal (Blaauw and Žagar 2018; Ryu et al. 2008; Žagar et al. 2022).

Such major peak is characterized by an eastward tilt, showing a progression from the amplification in the lower TTL where the strongest easterlies occur, to the upper TTL, where the increasing value of static stability N^2 allows effective propagation; both features are considered to be a characteristic fingerprint of the KW signal variance, and have been observed with the same decomposition also by Žagar et al. (2022) in the ERA5 dataset.

Two secondary peaks are located over the African and American continents. This latter is stronger in the DJF season, and can be associated to the strong variability in deep

Figure 4.14.: KW zonal wind subseasonal variability in the analysis fields. Averaged between latitude 15N and 15S.

convection found over land when the ITCZ is located close and south to the equator. The peak over African continent is less visible during the JJA season since it is incorporated by the westward shift of the main peak discussed *supra*.

4.2.2. KW errors

Here are reported results about forecast errors for the KW, in two separate subsection respectively for the systematic and random errors.

Results on KW mean signal and variability revealed fundamentally two identities of the KW: a first one, to be found in the mean, static features, as a forced pattern representing zonal convective circulation cells and confined below the lower TTL; a second one, provided by the variability, showing the transient features of the KW within the framework of upward and eastward propagating gravity waves. Mean signals provide a background state for the propagation of gravity waves, that can lead to their effective propagation or, instead, dissipation.

The discussion of errors moves from this two-faced picture of the KW. Firstly, systematic errors are addressed in terms of tropospheric signal associated to circulation features, and revealing advection of systematic errors at longer lead times. Discussion of error variability (RMSE) reveals a more intricate picture, where earliest loss of predictability is to be found in the upper-mid troposphere. Correspondence or disagreement with the OLR footprints is evaluated as well.

Systematic errors

Figure 4.15 shows the KW zonal wind bias at forecast day 1. At this stage, bias is given by the propagation of observation and model systematic errors during the first 24 hours of run. The amplitude of day 1 bias is within ± 1 m/s, *i.e.* roughly 10% of the peak value found in the mean signal.

Similarly to the mean signal, peaks are found in the TTL. Besides that, the vertical structure of bias shows remarkable differences from the mean signal. The vertical extent of structure through the TTL is much larger and extends well above the 100 hPa model level. The amplitude of systematic errors in the lower stratosphere and mid-low troposphere is very close to the mean amplitudes found at those levels and totally comparable to the main peaks (compare with figure 4.12).

Most of the bias structures found in the TTL extend steeply in the vertical direction, with an eastward tilt. Steepness increases from the mid TTL into the stratosphere, where static stability is at its largest. This can be attributed to the propagation of errors during the first day of model run by the fastest-propagating gravity waves.

The main bias structures are characterized by a first baroclinic structure between the mid-low troposphere and the lower TTL in a very similar manner to the mean signal, reflecting the projection of the tropical zonal circulation cells on the KW modes. These

structures represent ‘virtual’ ascending and descending convective branches describing the systematic differences between forecast and observations.

America and Atlantic The most articulated bias structure is found between longitudes 90°W and 45°E . Firstly, this describes a virtual ascending branch around longitude 80°W , corresponding to the descending branch of the Walker circulation. This marks a strong correspondence with the wet bias over Peru/Colombia, especially strong during the DJF and MAM season.

Such structure of easterlies terminates in a virtual descending branch around longitude 30°W in the DJF and MAM seasons and around 45°W in the JJA and SON seasons. This corresponds straightforwardly to the dry bias during the DJF and MAM season.

As concerns the JJA and SON season, this westward displacement reflects the concurrent effect of two changes in OLR bias features found in those seasons (see figure 4.5): firstly, a shrinking toward the west of the wet Peru/Colombia bias; secondly, a weakening of the dry bias over the Atlantic and a strengthening of the dry bias over the eastern part of the South-American Continent.

Maritime Continent Above the region between longitudes 80°E and 150°E a large westerly bias structures is found in all seasons. At saturation, the local bias amplitude is 2 m/s (see bias at forecast day 5, figure 4.16).

As already mentioned *supra*, the Maritime continent constitutes the western edge of the Pacific Walker; such neat projection of the Walker Circulation on the KW signal is probably due to the persistent La Niña conditions during the entire period covered by this data set. As a consequence, a strengthening of the Walker circulation via Bjerknes’s positive feedback (Gill 1982; Holton 2004) is observed.

Eastward, the westerlies structure terminates over the Pacific, around longitude 160°W , in a virtual descending branch. Such feature has a correspondence with the generalized dry bias over the Western Pacific found in the OLR bias.

Westward, the westerlies structure terminates over the Indian Ocean, more precisely close to the African Continent, around longitude 45°E . More in the west, is clearly visible a strong discontinuity in signal reflecting East Africa’s topography. This part constitutes a virtual ascending branch over the Indian Ocean, and is not inconsistent with the displacement to the west of the convective barycenter of the large convective structure over the Maritime Continent, as seen *supra*.

Africa The bias pattern over the African Continent is tightly connected with both structures commented *supra* and is also characterized by a strong seasonality. During the DJF and MAM season, this consists in a stronger easterly signal in the forecasts than in the observations (compare with the mean signal, figure 4.12).

During the JJA and SON seasons, the bias structure over Africa is fragmented into smaller scale features. Particularly helpful is, in this case, the bias at forecast day 5 (figure

Figure 4.15.: Subseasonal KW zonal wind bias at forecast day 1. Dashed lines as in figure 4.12.

Figure 4.16.: As in figure 4.12 but for the bias at forecast day 5.

4.16), showing more clearly how these features develop as early-stage errors propagate upward and eastward with the model run.

Around 10°E there is a virtual ascending branch, which insists on the central part of the African Continent. Such ascending branch has a correspondence with a bias structure covering the regions occupied the by Congo river rainforests. Such wet bias is actually strong also during the MAM season, but probably masked by the presence of a strong dry structure over Western Africa, which is instead dissipated during the JJA and SON seasons.

Between 30°E and 40°E there is a virtual descending branch during all seasons. This is particularly visible during the JJA and SON seasons, but can be recognized in the strong westerly winds occurring in the mid-lower troposphere also in the DJF and MAM season. This bias structure has a correspondence with the generalized dry bias over Eastern Africa found in the OLR signal.

The vertical propagation of errors originating over the African Continent (see figure 4.16) is majestic. This is possible thanks to the strong background of easterlies offering favorable conditions for the upward propagation of gravity waves, especially during the JJA and SON seasons. This indicates that errors systematically generated over this region, whose features are initially in the synoptic scales, with increasing forecast length have repercussions at planetary scales, throughout the entire TTL and into the stratosphere. This peculiarity is evident when put into comparison with errors originating over the American Continent: the westerly background isolates them into the lower TTL, so that their propagation upward is penalized.

Random errors

Error variability (RMSE, not shown) in the KW zonal wind at forecast day 5 follows closely the main structures of the signal variability (RMSD, figure 4.14), together with its westward shift in the JJA season discussed *supra*. However, relative errors reveal a different pictures, that concerns especially model levels in the upper-troposphere, where signal variability is low.

Relative Errors Figure 4.17 shows the evolution of KW zonal wind normalized RMSE for the DJF season. The shown quantity is computed as:

$$\frac{\text{RMSE}(u)_{l,s}(\lambda, \phi)}{\text{RMSD}(u)_{0,s}(\lambda, \phi)} \quad (4.5)$$

where lead time 0 indicates the analysis.

Strikingly, errors at forecast day 1 are already above 20% of the climatological standard deviation over the entire considered domain, indicating large uncertainties in the initial state. The earliest onset of growth for relative errors is located in the upper-troposphere, around model levels 350 hPa, above all continents, and is also where the earliest loss of

Figure 4.17.: Subseasonal error variability (RMSE) during the DJF season for the KW zonal wind forecasts normalized by the standard deviation of the analysis.

predictability is found.

The main relative error structure insists over the Maritime Continent and Indian Ocean and locally exceed values of 0.4 already at forecast day 1.

A second structure, located over the Western Atlantic and South-American Continent (between 80°W and 30°W) extends vertically throughout into the TTL. A third structure is located in the lower troposphere (model levels between 550 hPa and 850 hPa) and insists over the African Continent (between 0° and 30°E).

Predictability of the KW around model level 350 hPa especially above the Indian Ocean and Maritime Continent is almost completely lost by day 3 and approaches theoretical saturation by forecast day 5. On the one hand, this has little reflection on the evaluation of the total KW signal, since these levels are characterized by tiny KW amplitudes. On the other hand, this indicates a precise localization for sources of errors in the upper troposphere, that could eventually propagate into the TTL as lead time increases. This may be associated to specific model settings in convection simulation over regions characterized by strong convection that we are at this stage not aware of.

4.3. The KW in spectral space

This section presents result related to KW in spectral space representation. A first subsection is related to the KW signal in fields and errors, and aims at clarifying the role of different sets of vertical modes in defining the structures described in section 4.2. The second and last subsection deals with results related to the separation of forecast errors into phase and amplitude contribution.

4.3.1. Signal and errors

Variability

Figure 4.18 shows the spectral distribution of the total KW subseasonal squared variability (MSD) in analysis and forecast fields with respect to zonal wave-number. The KW has a remarkably red spectrum showing the striking predominance of planetary scales ($k = 1, \dots, 5$). These incorporate around 85% of the total signal variance, while the explained variance increases to values well above 95% when including also the synoptic scales ($k = 1, \dots, 16$).

Zonal spectra reveal also strong seasonality in the planetary and synoptic scales KW signal, with almost a factor 2 in squared variability between the seasons with the strongest (DJF, JJA) and the weakest (MAM, SON) KW signal.

The vertical perspective Figure 4.19 provides the spectral distribution of squared variability (MSD) with respect to vertical mode m . Here the difference in variance between seasons is even more evident, and concentrated in the largest equivalent depths.

Figure 4.18.: Total KW spectral variance with respect to zonal wavenumber k in the analysis (darkest) and forecast days 1 to 10 (to lighter colors with increasing lead time), from left to right and top to bottom for the DJF, MAM, JJA and SON seasons.

Figure 4.19.: As in figure 4.19, but with respect to the vertical mode m .

Figure 4.20.: KW zonal wind subseasonal variability (RMSD) in the analysis for the DJF and JJA seasons. From top to bottom, only the fast ($m = 1, \dots, 4$), the mid ($m = 5, \dots, 9$) and the slow ($m = 10, \dots, 39$) modes are considered. Signal is averaged between latitudes 15N and 15S. Dashed lines delimit the ISA tropopause ($\sim 216 - 56$ hPa) and stratopause ($\sim 1.2 - 0.6$ hPa).

The analysis carries the highest value of subseasonal variability in all vertical modes and throughout all seasons (especially MAM and SON), and that this quantity shrinks in forecast fields as lead time increases.

Around 40% of the total variance is incorporated in the vertical modes $m = 1, \dots, 9$, another 40% in modes $m = 10, \dots, 20$, while the spectrum between two minor peaks $m = 21, \dots, 40$ carries a contribution of more than 10% to the total variance.

Peaks MSD peaks around vertical mode $m = 9$ (equivalent depth 302 m), for all seasons. In the DJF and SON seasons the peak is duller, and involves also vertical mode $m = 8$ (equivalent depth 390 m), while in the MAM season the peak is on vertical mode $m = 10$ (equivalent depth 240 m). These spectra are completely consistent with those computed by Žagar et al. (2022) on the ERA5 dataset.

Secondary peaks appear in all seasons around vertical mode $m = 18$ (equivalent depth 72 m), $m = 27$ (equivalent depth 36 m) and $m = 36$ (equivalent depth 18 m). Žagar et al. (2022) have put these peaks in relation with the range of equivalent depths spanned by the KW filtering performed by Wheeler and Kiladis (1999) and found they mainly come from spectral coefficients in the $k = 1$ zonal mode; the authors further speculate that this can indicate KW propagation at very low phase speeds, with periods up to 30-50 days and are associated with ‘stratiform diabatic heating’ below the tropopause.

Contribution of vertical modes

Figure 4.20 shows the KW zonal wind variability in physical representation separated by vertical modes. The groups defined for back-projection are the fast ($m = 1, \dots, 4$), the mid ($m = 5, \dots, 9$) and the slow ($m = 10, \dots, 39$) modes. The slow modes, spanning the secondary peaks along the descending slope of the spectra, are the largest contributors to the upper TTL variability, peaking in the eastern hemisphere (compare with figure 4.14).

During the JJA season there is an eastward tilt traversing the the TTL from longitude 30°E , which can be associated to the effective upward propagation of gravity waves during the period of strongest easterly background signal.

The contribution of the fast modes to variability is very small (below 3 m/s) and only above the tropopause; strikingly large contribution to the variance in the upper stratosphere and above comes from both the mid and slow vertical modes groups.

Means and Bias Figure 4.21 shows the bias for the same selection of vertical modes during the DJF and JJA seasons. Also for the mean fields, the contribution to the mean signal from the fastest modes ($m = 1, \dots, 4$) is negligible below the stratosphere.

The mid ($m = 5, \dots, 9$) modes, instead, are strong contributors to the mean signal (not shown), and occupy the entire TTL with a strong signal associated to the zonal convective cells. As a reflection, the bias in those modes is similarly very close to a ‘textbook’ description of the associated first-baroclinic structure.

The slow ($m = 10, \dots, 29$) modes contribute significantly to the mean signal everywhere below the stratosphere. With respect to the mid modes, their role is generally to reinforce the signal in the lower TTL and to cancel it in the upper TTL, leading to the confinement of the zonal mean winds below 100 hPa noted *supra* (see figure 4.12).

In addition to that, the slow modes are those on which project the advection of error towards the upper TTL and the stratosphere, visible in the tilted structures extending in the eastern hemisphere. When comparing the DJF and JJA season, we can also appreciate the westward displacement of the entire region where propagation is facilitated, corresponding to the structure of easterlies (compare with figure 4.11).

All vertical modes carry relatively strong bias contributions in the highest model level, *i.e.* upper stratosphere and above, while the mean signal fades rapidly above the lower stratosphere for modes $m > 4$ (not shown). In the upper stratosphere, the slowest ($m = 10, \dots, 29$) modes show several eastward tilted bias structures, indicating advection of systematic errors from below.

Random errors Relative errors have been computed in spectral space, with respect to zonal wavenumber k and vertical mode m . Contraction of along the spectral index is done by summing variances:

$$\frac{(\text{RMSE}_{l,s})^k}{(\text{RMSD}_{0,s})^k} \equiv \frac{\sqrt{\sum_m (\text{MSE}_{l,s})_m^k}}{\sqrt{\sum_m (\text{MSD}_{0,s})_m^k}} \quad (4.6)$$

$$\frac{(\text{RMSE}_{l,s})_m}{(\text{RMSD}_{0,s})_m} \equiv \frac{\sqrt{\sum_k (\text{MSE}_{l,s})_m^k}}{\sqrt{\sum_k (\text{MSD}_{0,s})_m^k}} \quad (4.7)$$

with the same notation used *supra*.

The smallest relative initial errors are found at the planetary scales ($k = 1, \dots, 5$), below 0.3 at forecast day 1 (not shown); these modes have also the highest predictability, spanning from more than 10 days for $k = 1$ to 4 days for $k = 5$ throughout all seasons (compare with Buizza and Leutbecher (2015) on predictability at largest scales).

Figure 4.22 shows the relative errors with respect to vertical mode m . Predictability is surprisingly uniform across the entire spectrum, exception made for the fast ($m = 1, \dots, 4$) modes, especially in the MAM and SON seasons. For the fast modes initial relative errors are the largest, typically between 0.4 and 0.6 at forecast day 1.

For what concerns the mid and slow modes ($m > 4$) initial relative errors are significantly smaller and always below 0.4; in particular, the shape roughly follows the same bell observed in the signal variance (compare with figure 4.19), but turned upside down.

For all the $m > 4$ modes the 0.6 threshold for relative errors is reached around day 4, in line with the evaluation of relative error growth in physical space in the troposphere and tropopause layer (compare with figure 4.17).

The earliest loss of predictability is in the modes $m = 40, \dots, 60$. The relative errors for

Figure 4.21.: KW zonal wind forecast day 5 bias for the DJF (left) and JJA (right) seasons. From top to bottom, only the fastest ($m = 1, \dots, 4$), the mid ($m = 5, \dots, 9$) and the slow ($m = 10, \dots, 29$) modes are considered.

Figure 4.22.: error standard deviation with respect to vertical mode m normalized by standard deviation of the analysis in forecast days 1 to 10 (darker to lighter colors with increasing lead time)

these modes mainly project in the tropopause (not shown), and are thus dominated by the earliest error growth found around model level 350 hPa (compare with figure 4.17). Nonetheless, the errors appearing at this model level project on all the slower modes $m > 10$ (not shown), therefore it was not possible to trace a more precise association to errors in spectral coefficients.

4.3.2. Separation of phase/amplitude errors

This subsection presents result of the procedure for separating phase and amplitude errors. Firstly, results related to phase shifts are presented, showing that forecasts tend to produce slower KW in the mid and lower stratosphere. Finally, results related to amplitude errors are reported, showing that forecasts KWs have less and less variability as forecast lead time increases.

Phase shifts

Figure 4.24 show the results of the phase-amplitude amplitude separation procedure for the KW forecast errors for all planetary- and synoptic-scale modes $k = 1, \dots, 16$ in the

Figure 4.23.: Vertical profile of Kelvin wave zonal wind total errors (RMSE, gray lines) and errors attributed to phase shift (dark to light green with increasing lead time $RMSE_{ph}$). Forecast lead times 1, 3, 5, 9 days.

DJF and MAM seasons. Results are presented with respect to vertical model level, *i.e.* in physical space representation.

Overview of statistics The top plots of each figure shows the total squared amplitude ratio between error data suited for separation and all available errors, r_{sep} ; we recall here that separation can be performed only when the condition $\delta \in [-\pi, \pi]$ applies. r_{sep} is larger than 0.75 for lead times 1 to 3 days; and progressively shrinks to around 0.5 by day 10.

The plots in between show the ratio between the error variance attributed to a phase shift over the entire error variance of the samples for which separation was applied, r_{ph} . Its value is always larger than 0.5 and tends to grow toward 0.6. Phase contribution to the error variance is within this framework substantial and shows an increasing role of the pure phase term.

The bottom plots show the ratio of error variance attributable to an eastward phase shift, r_{east} . This quantity was constructed to investigate whether phase shifts are strongly biased toward a specific direction.

Errors Before commenting on the phase shift direction, we shall refer to figure 4.23, showing the vertical profile of errors for the KW zonal wind, for the quantities $RMSE_{l,s}$

and for $(\text{RMSE}_{ph})_{l,s}$ at selected lead times 1, 3, 5 and 9 days. Levels above the mid-stratosphere are ignored in order to obtain a more detailed depiction for the lower levels.

RMSE profile follows closely that of RMSD in the KW signal (compare with figure 4.13), with the main peak in TTL, around 100 hPa (see discussion *supra*). RMSE_{ph} follows the same shape, but scaled by a factor around 0.6, in line with the statistics r_{ph} .

RMSE at forecast day 5 are roughly between 60% and 70% of the RMSD in the analysis fields, and RMSE_{ph} around 35% and 40%.

East and West shifts In the troposphere, there is no significant predominance of either direction in phase shift, and this vanishes in any case very rapidly with increasing forecast lead times.

In the lower TTL (below 100 hPa), more than 60% of the phase error variance at short lead time ($l = 2, \dots, 5$) is given by a westward shift. This is the level characterized by the strongest background winds (see figure 4.12), where waves are expected to be generated and start propagate upward.

Just above the 100 hPa there is a slight dominance of contribution attributed to eastward shifts, between 60% and 70%, stronger in the MAM season. This is also the level where the main peak in KW variability is found (compare with figure 4.13), and indicates a tendency of the forecasts to faster KW propagation. Such shift shrinks rapidly for longer forecasts, probably indicating rapid loss of forecast skill in phase. In spectral representation, this behaviour is reflected by the fast and mid modes $m = 1, \dots, 9$ (not shown).

In the mid and lower stratosphere, there is a strong predominance of westward shifts, throughout all seasons. This predominance typically peaks with values around 0.2 except for the JJA, around 0.4 (not shown). As already seen *supra*, variability at these levels is associated with upward propagation of the KW from the TTL. We recall that here variability is at its strongest thanks to background easterlies and large buoyancy.

The westward shift prevalence in the stratosphere spans a wide range of model levels between 10 hPa and 56 hPa, with a value of the ratio r_{ph} between 0.3 and 0.2.

With increasing forecast lead time, r_{sep} shows that the phase errors δ tend to spread also out of the domain for separation $[\pi/2, \pi/2]$, so that by day 10, slightly more than 50% of δ are subject to separation.

In the null hypothesis of a uniform distribution of δ , representing complete decorrelation between forecast and verifying field, exactly 50% of values are expected to be in the domain for separation.

However, all addressed shift prevalence in the TTL and the lower stratosphere, is maintained with increasing forecast lead time, which shows that they conserve a preferred direction, located in the positive or negative values of the domain $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$.

Figure 4.24.: From top to bottom the values of r_{sep} , r_{ph} and r_{east} for the KW zonal wind signal with respect to vertical model level, for the KW signal in the DJF (left) and MAM (right) seasons. Values are computed an zonal wave-numbers $k = 1, \dots, 16$. Each line corresponds to forecast lead time from 1 to 10 from darker to lighter color.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

This section briefly summarizes and discusses the main findings of this work, explicitly addressing the two research questions. Finally, conclusions are drawn, with an opening toward possible future directions of investigation.

5.1. KW and OLR errors

OLR has been used as a proxy for deep tropical convection over the three-years period 2019-2021; in addition to that, spectral coefficients for the KW provided by 3DNM decomposition of the operational deterministic ECMWF forecast and analysis fields have been used for the period period September 2019 to September 2022. Deployed methodology consisted in pointing out large scale regional features in the tropical OLR signal, as well as in systematic and random errors, and relate them to the KW fields.

Means and circulation cells

The mean vertical structure of the KW signal consists of a first-baroclinic mode and the horizontal wavenumber $k = 1$, with largest amplitude signal confined in the lower part of the TTL, below 100 hPa. The overall planetary structure reflects the circulation associated to zonal convective cells whose ascending branches are located on continents.

The mean KW has amplitude around 6 m/s and a strong intraseasonal variation; in particular, there is a westward displacement of the easterlies structure (above the Indian Ocean) during the JJA season. This has been associated with an analogous displacement of the peak OLR signal (mean and variability) along the NW-SE direction along the Maritime and Asian Continents.

Errors

Systematic errors in the KW (KW biases) peak around 2 m/s are interpreted in terms of “virtual” circulation cells, with ascending and descending convective branches. For the OLR biases regions with negative values have been associated to “wetter” conditions in forecasts than in observations, while positive biases to too “dry” forecasts. The magnitude of biases is up to 30% of the mean signal for the KW, and up to 50% for the OLR.

We assessed the correspondence with OLR large-scale patterns for a wet bias over Peru/Colombia (all seasons) and a dry bias over the Eastern Atlantic (DJF and MAM,

displacing toward the west in JJA and SON). Bias structures over the Maritime Continent showed a virtual ascending branch over the Indian Ocean and a virtual descending branch over the Western Pacific, reflecting a dry bias particularly strong east of the Maritime Continent.

Systematic errors over the African continent can be associated to the large synoptic scales. These reflect only to a limited extent a “wet” bias around longitude 10°E but quite strongly a “dry” bias over Eastern Africa, especially in the JJA and SON seasons.

Most importantly, KW biases over the African Continent and Indian Ocean reflect systematic propagation of errors from the lower TTL to the lower stratosphere. This happens thanks to the local easterly background in the TTL, allowing for effective upward propagation of gravity waves. The shape of error structures is steeper and deeper-reaching during the JJA and SON seasons, when the TTL easterlies found in the mean signal are stronger.

Variability and RMSE

KW variability peaks over the Indian Ocean around 100 hPa and is characterized by significant amplitude throughout the stratosphere. This is partially associated to the upward propagation of the KWs from the upper troposphere and the lower stratosphere. We also showed that variability at those levels project almost entirely on the slow ($m = 10, \dots, 39$) vertical modes. The large KW variability in the upper stratosphere has been associated instead to diurnal tides.

The fastest growth of the KW forecast errors takes place over continents, whereas the largest short-term (<5 days) error growth occurs in the upper tropopause, around level 300 hPa. Such errors are located over continents and at levels where strong convection typically occurs. This may be related to some specific model configuration that we are currently not aware of. This distribution of errors is also partially reflected in the OLR RMSE where largest initial errors are found over the African Continent.

Connections between KW and OLR errors

The first research question concerned the possibility of connecting errors in simulated convection and those in the KW forecasts. This question has great relevance for the understanding of the impact of simulated convection on short-term (<5 days) forecast skill in the tropics. Results have shown a reflection of bias structures between OLR and KW fields, for several regions in the tropical belt.

It was possible to find a close correspondence between systematic errors in OLR and KW. These are present already at forecast day 1 and grow in amplitude with increasing forecast lead time, settling around day 5. The growth rate is in line with the short time scales characterizing convection (Kalnay 2003) and repercussion of model deficiencies during the assimilation phase (Žagar 2017).

While in the troposphere and lower TTL (below 100 hPa) OLR and KW fields show a tight coupling, systematic errors in the upper TTL and lower stratosphere reflect a propagation regime of internal gravity waves. This allows to trace back biases at those levels to errors in convection simulation, especially over the African continent, systematically occurring during early stages of forecast runs.

5.2. The phase errors

A method for separating phase and amplitude contribution to forecast errors has been presented. This consisted in applying, for each point in spectral space, a rotation of the spectral coefficients. Such rotation has been designed in such a way that, whenever the phase difference δ is within the definition domain $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, the imaginary part of the rotated errors is attributed to phase shifts, and the real part to errors in amplitude. Separated errors account for more than 75% of the entire error variance during the first 3 days of forecast. This ratio decreases gradually to slightly above 50% by day 10.

In all model levels below 10 hPa, RMSE attributed to phase shift has an amplitude of roughly 60% of the total variability in separated errors. Vertical profile of RMSE follows, in shape, the signal variance, with a peak around 100 hPa in the TTL and significant error variability in the lower-mid stratosphere.

In correspondence to the peak variability, around 100 hPa, error variance attributed to eastward shifts is around 60% of the total phase error variance, which may indicate a tendency of the model to propagate too fast KWs in the region of maximum amplification.

A compelling result of this decomposition concerns a large number of model levels spanning the lower stratosphere, roughly between 50 hPa and 10 hPa, where between 70% and 80% of the phase error variance shall be attributed to westward shift of the KW in the forecast fields. At these levels, characterized by significant variability of the KW signal due to upward propagation from the lower TTL, forecast KW tend to propagate slower than in the verifying fields.

Addressing phase errors

The second research question concerned the possibility of exploiting the complex notation of KW spectral coefficients to separate forecast errors into phase shift and amplitude contributions. Given the eastward phase speed of the KWs, this can have an interpretation in terms of over- or under-estimation of the KW propagation speed in forecasts.

The devised method offers a way to attribute error variances either to errors in phase or amplitude. Like other discussed methods, this comes with some compromise in description. In particular, it does not provide any specific information on the amount of the shift, in terms *e.g.* of phase speed. However, while providing only a binary indication (eastward or westward shift), it is able to quantify the impact of each of those on the error variance for phase shifts. While an indication about such shift could be successfully ex-

tracted from our data, strong factual conclusions about systematic model errors in phase is hard to achieve.

In order to address the question, the error separation approach probably offers too blurry a picture to effectively settle it. In particular, the greatest issue is that the amount of separated errors declines very rapidly with lead time, partially reflecting decline in forecast skill in phase, but probably also a distortion effect that could not be effectively tackled with back-projection onto physical space. This indicates that limited information may come from a method intrinsically designed as ‘one size fit all’, especially considering the wide span of scales and the different regimes characterizing the KW.

5.3. Conclusions

While the structure of this work followed closely the addressing of two specific research questions, it also illustrated, though with limited, self-educational aim, aspects related to the concept of KW as a convectively-coupled wave.

OLR fields proved key in tracing a correspondence between deep tropical convection and the observed mean and bias structures of the KW. However, KW systematic errors, in the lower TTL reflecting the OLR signal, match in the stratosphere and above systematic upward advection by gravity waves. We tried to make a point on how this example provides one of the possible realization of such convection-wave coupling when dealing with forecast errors.

More generally, KWs appear to have a double nature. One nature is observed in the mean signals forced on time scales at least of the season, and closely reflects circulation patterns sound with the planetary scale tropical zonal circulation cells. A second one concerns all the perturbations happening on this “canvas”, as convectively-coupled wave forced on time scales of the day. These perturbations get amplified in the mid tropopause and finally propagate freely toward the stratosphere.

Variability structures show that upper propagation of waves and errors is associated with the background of easterlies extending over African Continent and Indian Ocean. This shall imply that forecast errors on the African Continent have more of a far reaching impact than those originating *e.g.* from the American Continent, due to the isolating layer provided by the background of westerlies in the TTL over the western hemisphere.

Further investigation of this research question should take into account also precipitation data in order to clarify the correspondence between forecast errors and convection. In addition to that, I believe that including at least the first equatorial Rossby Wave modes may provide a better representation of such coupling within 3DNM representation also in the height fields, that were almost completely neglected during this work.

As concerns the separation of phase and forecast errors, the developed method was preferred over the phase difference method for it provided a quantification in terms of explained error variance.

A shortcoming of the phase/amplitude error separation method is that it does not provide a quantification in terms of typical phase shift or phase speed error. Clearly, also these aspects are relevant for defining phase shift errors and shall be explored, in order to fully tackle the research question. Moreover, some intrinsic limitations of such approach should be considered; these could be overcome by including explicitly vertical distortion of features and separated treatment of the KW regimes, *e.g.* into the lower and the upper TTL. A possible future investigation may also concern the decomposition of error variance into the pure phase, amplitude and mixed terms; this would require clarifying what are the expected values of these terms *e.g.* in a perfect forecast, and what instead they can say when dealing with forecast verification.

A. Vertical structure and LRSW

As anticipated *supra*, the LRSW equations 2.4 and 2.5 lead to the Laplace's tidal equations of which the equatorial beta-plane theory constitute an approximation (Matsuno 1966). By noticing in the LRSW equations that:

$$f = 2\Omega \sin \phi \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$y = a \sin \phi \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where Ω is the Earth's rotation frequency and ϕ is the latitude coordinate, an equation for the non-dimensional variable \tilde{h} can be obtained (Kasahara 2020, p. 22):

$$\Xi \tilde{h} + \epsilon \tilde{h} = 0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\Xi \equiv \frac{d}{d\mu} \left[\left(\frac{1 - \mu^2}{v^2 - \mu^2} \right) \frac{d}{d\mu} \right] + \frac{1}{v^2 - \mu^2} \left[\frac{k(v^2 + \mu^2)}{v(v^2 - \mu^2)} - \frac{k^2}{1 - \mu^2} \right] \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\tilde{h}(\mu) = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \mu = -1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mu = +1 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where $\mu = \sin \phi$, and $\epsilon = \frac{4a^2\Omega^2}{gD}$ is called Lamb's parameter, a non-dimensional quantity combining the Earth's radius a , angular velocity Ω , gravity g and equivalent depth D . One can recognize equation A.3 as an eigenvalue problem for the field \tilde{h} with eigenvalue ϵ for an operator Ξ .

Separation of variables There is a sequence of separations of variables needed to deploy the LRSW equations in a 3-dimensional problem. In a first stage, the problem is a system of four equations, including a thermodynamic equation, in four variables: three spatial dimensions and time. The solution is investigated by using the technique of the separation of variables:

$$(u', v', P')(\lambda, \phi, \sigma, t) = (\hat{u}, \hat{v}, g\hat{h})(\lambda, \phi, t) G(\sigma) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $\sigma \equiv \frac{p}{p_s}$ is the pressure vertical coordinate. The dependency on the vertical coordinate variable can thus be separated in order to obtain the above-presented equations 2.4 and 2.5 and a separated problem for the vertical structure function (VSF) $G(\sigma)$ (Kasahara

Figure A.1.: VSFs solved for the EMCWF HRES model levels between 0.4 hPa and 990 hPa. Within each plot, lines have the same sequence of color of increasing vertical modes: blue, orange, green, red, purple.

2020):

$$\frac{d}{d\sigma} \left(\frac{\sigma}{S} \frac{dG}{d\sigma} \right) + \mu G = 0 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\frac{dG}{d\sigma} + \frac{\Gamma_0}{T_0} G = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \sigma = 1 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\sigma \frac{dG}{d\sigma} = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \sigma = \sigma_{TOP} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where $S \equiv \frac{R\Gamma_0}{gH_s}$ is a dimensionless stability factor depending on lapse rate Γ_0 and surface elevation H_s and $\mu \equiv \frac{H_s}{D}$ is the inverse-scaled equivalent depth. σ_{TOP} indicates the value of σ at the model's top layer. One can notice by multiplying equation A.7 by the factor S that the problem's eigenvalue can be expressed in a form invariant to atmospheric stability, as $(S\mu)$: this shows that the equivalent depth is directly proportional to stability Γ_0 , reflecting also the intuition that a more stratified atmosphere constitutes a more rigid propagation mean for gravity waves and, by consequence, higher phase speeds can be expected.

Figure A.1 shows VSFs solved for the ECMWF HRES model levels in groups of increasing mode number from $m = 1$ to $m = 39$. As a rule of thumb, vertical mode sets are expected to contribute mostly to those levels where they show a high coherence; where the coherence is low they tend to interfere destructively. For this reason, vertical modes $m = 1, \dots, 4$ can be attributed to represent a barotropic profile spanning the stratosphere and tropopause layers; modes $m = 5, \dots, 9$ incorporate at the same levels a first baroclinic structure, $m = 10, \dots, 14$ a second baroclinic structure and so on. Moreover, increasing modes have VSFs that are coherent closer and closer to the lower levels: e.g. the coherent part for the VSFs corresponding to modes $m = 34, \dots, 39$ is totally confined in the troposphere.

Sturm-Liouville's problems A Sturm-Liouville's problem for the function u in the variable x is formally given by the following:

$$\frac{1}{\rho(x)} \left[\frac{d}{dx} \left(p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \right) - q(x) \right] u(x) - \lambda u(x) \quad x \in [\alpha, \beta] \subset \mathbb{R} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$u(\alpha) = u(\beta) = 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where $p(x) > 0 \in \mathcal{C}^1$, $q(x) \geq 0 \in \mathcal{C}^0$ and $\rho(x) > 0 \in \mathcal{C}^0$. $\rho(x)$ is a weight function that defines a scalar product:

$$(f, g)_\rho \equiv \int_\alpha^\beta f^*(x)g(x)\rho(x)dx \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Two fundamental properties of such problem are:

1. eigenvalues λ of the problem are all real and greater than zero;
2. the orthogonal eigenfunctions $\{u_n(x)\}$ constitute a complete set of L^2 with respect

m	D_m	$k = 1$	$k = 2$	$k = 3$	$k = 4$	$k = 5$	$k = 6$	$k = 7$	$k = 8$	$k = 9$
1	10024	63	127	191	255	319	382	446	510	574
3	3347	36	73	110	147	184	221	258	294	331
5	1106	21	42	63	84	105	127	148	169	190
7	519	14	29	43	58	72	87	101	116	130
9	301	11	22	33	44	55	66	77	88	99
11	194	8	17	26	35	44	53	62	71	80
13	138	7	15	22	30	37	45	52	60	67
15	103	6	12	19	25	32	38	45	51	58
17	80	5	11	17	22	28	34	40	45	51
19	64	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	41	46
21	54	4	9	14	18	23	28	32	37	42
23	46	4	8	13	17	21	26	30	34	39
25	41	4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36
27	35	3	7	11	15	19	22	26	30	34

Table A.1.: Absolute phase change values in degrees per hour for a selection of KW modes with zonal wavenumber k and vertical mode m . For each vertical mode m also the corresponding equivalent depth D_m is reported.

to the scalar product defined in equation A.12, *i.e.* for all functions f such that:

$$(f, f)_\rho < +\infty \quad (\text{A.13})$$

By consequence, the vertical structure function $G(\sigma)$ can be decomposed in terms of vertical eigenfunctions, solutions of the Sturm-Liouville's problem defined by equation A.7 together with boundary conditions A.8 and A.9. In particular, each vertical mode is associated to an eigenvalue μ , which defines in turn an equivalent depth D . Once the vertical structure problem is solved, the horizontal problem, dictated by equations A.3, A.4 and A.5, is well defined for each equivalent depth D .

Wave propagation In the LRSW system, waves propagation is represented by rotating spectral coefficients in the complex plane. The time evolution of a spectral coefficient is given by a rotation:

$$\chi(t) = \chi_0 e^{i\phi(t)} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\phi(t) = -\omega t = -ck^*t \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where k^* is the zonal component of the wave vector, given by:

$$k^* = \frac{2\pi}{R_T} k \quad (\text{A.16})$$

with $R_T = 6.3 \cdot 10^6$ m the Earth's radius. Since for the KW $c = \sqrt{gD_m}$, the rate for phase change is:

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} = -\sqrt{gD_m} \frac{2\pi}{R_T} k \quad (\text{A.17})$$

As a reference, table A.1 reports absolute values of phase change rate for the KW in a selection of zonal wave-numbers k and vertical modes m . The range has been chosen as representative of most variability of the observed KW. The span of values describes the property of KW to incorporate a wide range of space and time scales.

B. Circular Statistics

When dealing with stochastic variables on a circular domain, concepts such as the arithmetic mean can make little sense. They can be used when the spread of data is very small around a central value, but in the general case they prove to be ill defined. To this end, we deploy here the following definition of a circular mean (or preferred) orientation (see *e.g.* Borradaile 2003) $\gamma_0 \in (-\pi, +\pi]$ for an angular stochastic variable $\gamma \in (-\pi, +\pi]$:

$$C \equiv \overline{\cos(\gamma(t))} \quad S \equiv \overline{\sin(\gamma(t))} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\gamma_0 \equiv \arg(C + iS) \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\bar{R} \equiv \sqrt{C^2 + S^2} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where \bar{R} is the *mean resultant length*, and proves essential for the interpretation of the statistic γ_0 . It is straightforward to see that $\bar{R} \in [0, 1]$, and that a value close to 1 indicates a strong preference along the mean orientation; a value close to 0 does not necessarily imply a uniform distribution, as the example of a perfectly bimodal-antipodal distribution may shows.

One can prove that the mean orientation defined by formula B.2 is equivariant under rotation, *i.e.* for any shift in the data (or for a domain shift) the mean orientations shifts by the same amount (Jammalamadaka and SenGupta 2001). Eventually \bar{R} can be rearranged in a formula that, in the limit of small deviations from the mean orientation, corresponds to the linear sample variance (Jammalamadaka and SenGupta 2001):

$$2(1 - \bar{R}) \approx s^2 \quad (\text{for small angle deviations}) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Polar plots Histograms on a polar projection, also called Rose diagrams, are a suitable mean for representing frequency of cyclical stochastic variables. Bins are slices of the disc representing the domain, and each slice's area is proportional to the number of data points falling into the interval. Number of bins have been decided starting basis from the following formula for the bin width w of a histogram given by Wilks 2019:

$$w \equiv \frac{c \text{ IQR}}{n^{1/3}} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where *IQR* stands for the inter-quantile range, and c is a values between 2 and 2.6. For the computation of the number of bins n_b on the circular domain, *IQR* has been evaluated as $\pi/3$, which is the variance of a uniform distribution on the domain $(-\pi, \pi]$, and $c = 2$

have been used:

$$n_b = \text{nat}(n^{1/3}) \tag{B.6}$$

$$w = \frac{2\pi}{3n_b} \tag{B.7}$$

where $\text{nat}(x)$ approximates the argument x to the closest natural number.

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